

Different Types and Aspects of Magic Squares of Order 18

The whole work is also available at author's sites:
<https://numbers-magic.com/?p=17001>

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Abstract

*This work summarizes author's previous works on magic squares of order 18. It brings different types of magic square such as **block-wise, single-digit bordered, double-digit bordered, cornered, designs, styles, etc.** In terms of aspects, we have considered the idea of **Pythagorean triples, perfect square sum entries, Latin square distributions, upside-down, mirror-looking, water reflection, algebraic magic squares, etc.***

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1 Introduction

In the previous works [19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25], the author worked with **block-wise** constructions of magic squares. The work is from the orders 8 to 45. In each case, all the possibilities are considered. These possibilities are based on divisions of magic squares. The magic sums of order n of consecutive numbers from 1 to n^2 is given by

$$S_{n \times n} := \frac{n \times (1 + n^2)}{2}, n \geq 3. \quad (1)$$

This formula is applied to all order magic squares. Based on this formula we shall bring **blocks** for the **block-wise** magic squares. That is, whenever is possible, we shall try to bring blocks of equal sum magic squares. In some cases, they are **magic, semi-magic, pandiagonal**, etc. When the question come to **bimagic** squares, in some cases, we have **semi-bimagic** squares.

On the other hand the idea of **bordered** magic squares is well explained in the work by H.White [4, 5]. Few results in this direction can be seen in author's work [26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31]. In some case, the magic rectangles are also used to write it in different styles. Most of the author's work on magic squares is summarized below in details according to topic:

1. *Digital Fonts: Upside-down and Mirror Looking.*
2. *Two Digits Universal Magic Squares.*
3. *Different Digits Magic Squares.*
4. *Pythagorean Triples Magic Squares.*
5. *Block-Wise Magic Squares.*
6. *Selfie and Palindromic Type Magic Squares.*
7. *Block Bordered Magic Squares.*
8. *Block-Wise Bordered Magic Squares.*
9. *Magic Crosses, Letters and Numbers.*
10. *Cornered Magic Squares.*
11. *Single-Digit Bordered Magic Squares.*
12. *Double-Digit Bordered Magic Squares.*
13. *Multiple-Digit Bordered Magic Squares.*
14. *Striped Magic Squares.*
15. *Upside-down and Mirror Looking.*
16. *Water reflection Magic Squares.*
17. *Algebraic Magic Squares.*

The aim of this work is to write magic squares of order 18 in different ways and styles using the aspects of **blocks, bordered, block-bordered** and **magic rectangles, corner-type, single-digit, double-digit**, etc.

More details on these works on **magic squares** can be seen in author's web-sites:

(i) <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=668>

(ii) <https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/2019/06/27/publications-magic-squares/>

2 Different Types of Magic Squares

According to Equation (1), the magic sum of order 18 is given by

$$S_{18 \times 18} := \frac{18 \times (1 + 18^2)}{2} = 2925.$$

We can write, $18 := 2 \times 3 \times 3$. This gives the possibility of blocks of orders 3 and 6. Let's see division of 2925 by 6 and 3:

$$(i) \quad \frac{2925}{6} = \frac{975}{2} \implies \text{non-equal blocks of order 3;}$$

$$(ii) \quad \frac{2925}{3} = 975 \implies \text{equal blocks of order 6.}$$

Below are few examples of different types of magic squares of order 18.

2.1 Block-Wise Magic Squares

Example 2.1. *Let's consider a magic square of order 18 given by*

mgc	Inder J. Taneja			https://inderjtaneja.com/			https://numbers-magic.com/			@IJTANEJA			©IJT			2925			
19	39	2	193	177	212	246	262	227	300	280	317	139	159	122	78	58	95	2925	
3	20	37	213	194	175	226	245	264	316	299	282	123	140	157	94	77	60	2925	
38	1	21	176	211	195	263	228	244	281	318	298	158	121	141	59	96	76	2925	
247	267	230	73	57	92	301	285	320	132	148	113	187	171	206	31	51	14	2925	
231	248	265	93	74	55	321	302	283	112	131	150	207	188	169	15	32	49	2925	
266	229	249	56	91	75	284	319	303	149	114	130	170	205	189	50	13	33	2925	
90	70	107	36	52	17	127	147	110	241	261	224	289	273	308	192	172	209	2925	
106	89	72	16	35	54	111	128	145	225	242	259	309	290	271	208	191	174	2925	
71	108	88	53	18	34	146	109	129	260	223	243	272	307	291	173	210	190	2925	
294	274	311	138	154	119	30	46	11	198	178	215	84	64	101	235	255	218	2925	
310	293	276	118	137	156	10	29	48	214	197	180	100	83	66	219	236	253	2925	
275	312	292	155	120	136	47	12	28	179	216	196	65	102	82	254	217	237	2925	
181	165	200	295	279	314	85	69	104	25	45	8	252	268	233	133	153	116	2925	
201	182	163	315	296	277	105	86	67	9	26	43	232	251	270	117	134	151	2925	
164	199	183	278	313	297	68	103	87	44	7	27	269	234	250	152	115	135	2925	
144	160	125	240	256	221	186	166	203	79	63	98	24	40	5	306	286	323	2925	
124	143	162	220	239	258	202	185	168	99	80	61	4	23	42	322	305	288	2925	
161	126	142	257	222	238	167	204	184	62	97	81	41	6	22	287	324	304	2925	
2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

It is composed of magic squares of order 3 with different magic sums

Example 2.2. *Let's consider a magic square of order 18 given by*

mgc	18x18 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/					https://numbers-magic.com/					@IJTANEJA		©IJT		2925			
1	307	306	289	18	54	2	308	305	290	17	53	3	309	304	291	16	52	2925
270	72	252	73	91	217	269	71	251	74	92	218	268	70	250	75	93	219	2925
216	199	127	144	180	109	215	200	128	143	179	110	214	201	129	142	178	111	2925
162	126	181	198	145	163	161	125	182	197	146	164	160	124	183	196	147	165	2925
55	234	90	235	253	108	56	233	89	236	254	107	57	232	88	237	255	106	2925
271	37	19	36	288	324	272	38	20	35	287	323	273	39	21	34	286	322	2925
4	310	303	292	15	51	5	311	302	293	14	50	6	312	301	294	13	49	2925
267	69	249	76	94	220	266	68	248	77	95	221	265	67	247	78	96	222	2925
213	202	130	141	177	112	212	203	131	140	176	113	211	204	132	139	175	114	2925
159	123	184	195	148	166	158	122	185	194	149	167	157	121	186	193	150	168	2925
58	231	87	238	256	105	59	230	86	239	257	104	60	229	85	240	258	103	2925
274	40	22	33	285	321	275	41	23	32	284	320	276	42	24	31	283	319	2925
7	313	300	295	12	48	8	314	299	296	11	47	9	315	298	297	10	46	2925
264	66	246	79	97	223	263	65	245	80	98	224	262	64	244	81	99	225	2925
210	205	133	138	174	115	209	206	134	137	173	116	208	207	135	136	172	117	2925
156	120	187	192	151	169	155	119	188	191	152	170	154	118	189	190	153	171	2925
61	228	84	241	259	102	62	227	83	242	260	101	63	226	82	243	261	100	2925
277	43	25	30	282	318	278	44	26	29	281	317	279	45	27	28	280	316	2925
2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

It is composed of equal sums magic squares of order 6.

For more details refer author's work [20, 22].

2.2 Single-Layer Bordered Squares

Example 2.3. Let's consider a magic square of order 18 given by

mgc	18x18	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	https://numbers-magic.com/	@IJTANEJA	©IJT	2925												
307	25	301	23	303	21	305	19	316	1	309	15	311	13	313	11	315	17	2925
298	276	56	270	54	53	273	274	283	268	48	47	279	45	281	43	50	27	2925
28	289	78	72	252	74	250	76	260	71	246	80	244	82	242	248	36	297	2925
296	37	259	224	233	93	231	95	91	112	214	110	216	108	223	66	288	29	2925
30	287	67	106	203	198	128	196	130	126	116	210	114	204	219	258	38	295	2925
294	39	257	105	125	138	132	192	194	181	143	183	137	200	220	68	286	31	2925
32	285	69	221	201	135	176	174	147	180	148	150	190	124	104	256	40	293	2925
292	41	255	222	123	136	146	161	166	155	168	179	189	202	103	70	284	33	2925
34	35	241	229	208	141	152	156	167	162	165	173	184	117	96	84	290	291	2925
26	64	235	218	113	191	154	170	157	164	159	171	134	212	107	90	261	299	2925
8	262	89	100	205	186	172	163	160	169	158	153	139	120	225	236	63	317	2925
318	62	237	99	119	185	175	151	178	145	177	149	140	206	226	88	263	7	2925
6	264	87	227	207	188	193	133	131	144	182	142	187	118	98	238	61	319	2925
320	60	239	97	121	127	197	129	195	199	209	115	211	122	228	86	265	5	2925
4	266	85	102	92	232	94	230	234	213	111	215	109	217	101	240	59	321	2925
322	58	77	253	73	251	75	249	65	254	79	245	81	243	83	247	267	3	2925
2	275	269	55	271	272	52	51	42	57	277	278	46	280	44	282	49	323	2925
308	300	24	302	22	304	20	306	9	324	16	310	14	312	12	314	10	18	2925
2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

It is single-layer bordered magic square. Removing the external bordered, still we left with less order magic squares, such as orders 16, 14, 12, etc.

Example 2.4. Let's consider a magic square of order 18 given by

mgc	18x18 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/					https://numbers-magic.com/					@IJTANEJA		©IJT		2925			
320	318	3	324	4	6	302	300	21	306	22	24	284	282	39	288	40	42	2925
2	17	310	11	312	323	20	35	292	29	294	305	38	53	274	47	276	287	2925
8	12	311	18	309	317	26	30	293	36	291	299	44	48	275	54	273	281	2925
10	314	13	308	15	315	28	296	31	290	33	297	46	278	49	272	51	279	2925
316	307	16	313	14	9	298	289	34	295	32	27	280	271	52	277	50	45	2925
319	7	322	1	321	5	301	25	304	19	303	23	283	43	286	37	285	41	2925
194	192	129	198	130	132	176	174	147	180	148	150	266	264	57	270	58	60	2925
128	143	184	137	186	197	146	161	166	155	168	179	56	71	256	65	258	269	2925
134	138	185	144	183	191	152	156	167	162	165	173	62	66	257	72	255	263	2925
136	188	139	182	141	189	154	170	157	164	159	171	64	260	67	254	69	261	2925
190	181	142	187	140	135	172	163	160	169	158	153	262	253	70	259	68	63	2925
193	133	196	127	195	131	175	151	178	145	177	149	265	61	268	55	267	59	2925
212	210	111	216	112	114	230	228	93	234	94	96	248	246	75	252	76	78	2925
110	125	202	119	204	215	92	107	220	101	222	233	74	89	238	83	240	251	2925
116	120	203	126	201	209	98	102	221	108	219	227	80	84	239	90	237	245	2925
118	206	121	200	123	207	100	224	103	218	105	225	82	242	85	236	87	243	2925
208	199	124	205	122	117	226	217	106	223	104	99	244	235	88	241	86	81	2925
211	115	214	109	213	113	229	97	232	91	231	95	247	79	250	73	249	77	2925
2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

It is composed of equal sums single-layer bordered magic squares of order 6.

Example 2.5. Let's consider a magic square of order 18 given by

mgc	18x18 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/				https://numbers-magic.com/				@IJTANEJA	©IJT	2925							
307	25	301	23	303	21	305	19	316	1	309	15	311	13	313	11	315	17	2925
298	41	286	35	288	49	278	43	280	57	270	51	272	65	262	59	264	27	2925
28	36	287	42	285	44	279	50	277	52	271	58	269	60	263	66	261	297	2925
296	290	37	284	39	282	45	276	47	274	53	268	55	266	61	260	63	29	2925
30	283	40	289	38	275	48	281	46	267	56	273	54	259	64	265	62	295	2925
294	129	198	123	200	137	190	131	192	145	182	139	184	73	254	67	256	31	2925
32	124	199	130	197	132	191	138	189	140	183	146	181	68	255	74	253	293	2925
292	202	125	196	127	194	133	188	135	186	141	180	143	258	69	252	71	33	2925
34	195	128	201	126	187	136	193	134	179	144	185	142	251	72	257	70	291	2925
26	121	206	115	208	161	166	155	168	153	174	147	176	81	246	75	248	299	2925
8	116	207	122	205	156	167	162	165	148	175	154	173	76	247	82	245	317	2925
318	210	117	204	119	170	157	164	159	178	149	172	151	250	77	244	79	7	2925
6	203	120	209	118	163	160	169	158	171	152	177	150	243	80	249	78	319	2925
320	113	214	107	216	105	222	99	224	97	230	91	232	89	238	83	240	5	2925
4	108	215	114	213	100	223	106	221	92	231	98	229	84	239	90	237	321	2925
322	218	109	212	111	226	101	220	103	234	93	228	95	242	85	236	87	3	2925
2	211	112	217	110	219	104	225	102	227	96	233	94	235	88	241	86	323	2925
308	300	24	302	22	304	20	306	9	324	16	310	14	312	12	314	10	18	2925
2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

It is a **single-layer bordered** magic square embedded with equal sums **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4. The magic squares of order 4 are also **pandiagonal**.

Example 2.6. Let's consider a magic square of order 18 given by

mgc	18x18	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	https://numbers-magic.com/	@IJTANEJA	©IJT	2925												
307	25	301	23	303	21	305	19	316	1	309	15	311	13	313	11	315	17	2925
298	42	36	288	290	277	47	279	41	74	68	256	258	245	79	247	73	27	2925
28	39	272	270	51	276	52	54	286	71	240	238	83	244	84	86	254	297	2925
296	40	50	65	262	59	264	275	285	72	82	97	230	91	232	243	253	29	2925
30	45	56	60	263	66	261	269	280	77	88	92	231	98	229	237	248	295	2925
294	287	58	266	61	260	63	267	38	255	90	234	93	228	95	235	70	31	2925
32	282	268	259	64	265	62	57	43	250	236	227	96	233	94	89	75	293	2925
292	281	271	55	274	49	273	53	44	249	239	87	242	81	241	85	76	33	2925
34	284	289	37	35	48	278	46	283	252	257	69	67	80	246	78	251	291	2925
26	138	132	192	194	181	143	183	137	106	100	224	226	213	111	215	105	299	2925
8	135	176	174	147	180	148	150	190	103	208	206	115	212	116	118	222	317	2925
318	136	146	161	166	155	168	179	189	104	114	129	198	123	200	211	221	7	2925
6	141	152	156	167	162	165	173	184	109	120	124	199	130	197	205	216	319	2925
320	191	154	170	157	164	159	171	134	223	122	202	125	196	127	203	102	5	2925
4	186	172	163	160	169	158	153	139	218	204	195	128	201	126	121	107	321	2925
322	185	175	151	178	145	177	149	140	217	207	119	210	113	209	117	108	3	2925
2	188	193	133	131	144	182	142	187	220	225	101	99	112	214	110	219	323	2925
308	300	24	302	22	304	20	306	9	324	16	310	14	312	12	314	10	18	2925
2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

It is a *single-layer bordered* magic square embedded with equal sums *single-layer* magic squares of order 8.

Example 2.7. Let's consider a magic square of order 18 given by

mgc	18x18	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	https://numbers-magic.com/	@IJTANEJA	©IJT	2925												
307	292	294	296	298	318	320	322	34	32	30	28	26	8	6	4	2	308	2925
25	46	280	281	43	42	284	285	39	78	248	249	75	74	252	253	71	300	2925
23	279	45	44	282	283	41	40	286	247	77	76	250	251	73	72	254	302	2925
21	35	289	288	38	47	277	276	50	67	257	256	70	79	245	244	82	304	2925
19	290	36	37	287	278	48	49	275	258	68	69	255	246	80	81	243	306	2925
15	59	265	264	62	58	268	269	55	91	233	232	94	90	236	237	87	310	2925
13	266	60	61	263	267	57	56	270	234	92	93	231	235	89	88	238	312	2925
11	54	272	273	51	63	261	260	66	86	240	241	83	95	229	228	98	314	2925
1	271	53	52	274	262	64	65	259	239	85	84	242	230	96	97	227	324	2925
301	110	216	217	107	106	220	221	103	142	184	185	139	138	188	189	135	24	2925
303	215	109	108	218	219	105	104	222	183	141	140	186	187	137	136	190	22	2925
305	99	225	224	102	111	213	212	114	131	193	192	134	143	181	180	146	20	2925
309	226	100	101	223	214	112	113	211	194	132	133	191	182	144	145	179	16	2925
311	123	201	200	126	122	204	205	119	155	169	168	158	154	172	173	151	14	2925
313	202	124	125	199	203	121	120	206	170	156	157	167	171	153	152	174	12	2925
315	118	208	209	115	127	197	196	130	150	176	177	147	159	165	164	162	10	2925
316	207	117	116	210	198	128	129	195	175	149	148	178	166	160	161	163	9	2925
17	33	31	29	27	7	5	3	291	293	295	297	299	317	319	321	323	18	2925
2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

It is a *single-layer bordered magic square* embedded with a *striped magic square* of order 16.

For more details refer author's work [22, 24]

2.3 Cornered Magic Square

Example 2.8. *Let's consider a magic square of order 18 given by*

mgc	18x18 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/				https://numbers-magic.com/				@IJTANEJA	©IJT	2925								
161	166	155	168	178	147	181	144	204	121	226	99	85	240	61	264	28	297	2925	
156	167	162	165	177	148	142	183	207	118	221	104	66	259	281	44	312	13	2925	
170	157	164	159	146	179	140	185	126	199	219	106	71	254	270	55	34	291	2925	
163	160	169	158	150	175	135	190	115	210	105	220	255	70	46	279	11	314	2925	
153	145	176	154	173	174	137	188	125	200	213	112	83	242	262	63	3	322	2925	
172	180	149	171	151	152	186	139	212	113	108	217	74	251	64	261	33	292	2925	
132	189	131	143	191	184	192	138	114	211	223	102	252	73	282	43	296	29	2925	
193	136	194	182	134	141	187	133	202	123	109	216	81	244	273	52	18	307	2925	
127	117	203	197	195	209	205	129	119	124	233	92	247	78	286	39	308	17	2925	
198	208	122	128	130	116	120	196	201	206	98	227	245	80	35	290	305	20	2925	
111	91	224	107	215	94	96	228	232	222	100	230	237	88	38	287	302	23	2925	
214	234	101	218	110	231	229	97	93	103	95	225	82	243	263	62	318	7	2925	
90	239	248	67	68	246	250	249	89	260	72	87	241	69	40	285	19	306	2925	
235	86	77	258	257	79	75	76	236	65	253	238	256	84	59	266	304	21	2925	
45	36	288	47	41	54	267	276	53	274	60	275	277	56	283	268	311	14	2925	
280	289	37	278	284	271	58	49	272	51	265	50	48	269	57	42	1	324	2925	
22	16	319	5	24	9	323	300	8	32	321	294	313	310	26	10	295	298	2925	
303	309	6	320	301	316	2	25	317	293	4	31	12	15	299	315	27	30	2925	
2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

It is a cornered magic square where in the upper-left corner we have lower order magic squares.

For more details refer author's work [36, 37, 38, 39].

2.4 Double-Layer Bordered Magic Squares

Example 2.9. *Let's consider a magic square of order 18 given by*

mgc	18x18	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	https://numbers-magic.com/	@IJTANEJA	©IJT	2925												
304	9	261	262	32	52	312	47	323	271	285	277	17	57	53	18	320	25	2925
316	21	64	63	293	273	13	278	2	54	40	48	308	268	272	307	300	5	2925
4	321	241	111	216	227	89	88	258	217	96	76	74	72	250	260	274	51	2925
46	279	214	84	109	98	236	237	67	108	229	249	251	253	65	75	29	296	2925
292	33	68	257	184	114	185	127	183	197	131	190	123	191	252	73	16	309	2925
27	298	103	222	211	141	140	198	142	128	194	135	134	202	215	110	280	45	2925
58	267	66	259	120	205	152	159	145	177	175	167	124	201	245	80	303	22	2925
319	6	246	79	119	206	162	180	179	148	160	146	133	192	90	235	263	62	2925
50	275	231	94	121	204	164	154	153	165	161	178	210	115	225	100	313	12	2925
286	39	102	223	199	126	171	168	151	166	147	172	125	200	85	240	59	266	2925
3	322	91	234	181	144	150	156	173	170	169	157	193	132	213	112	55	270	2925
310	15	238	87	122	203	176	158	174	149	163	155	187	138	247	78	24	301	2925
31	294	70	255	182	139	195	209	118	212	129	136	188	117	104	221	290	35	2925
269	56	256	69	186	143	130	116	207	113	196	189	208	137	71	254	7	318	2925
276	49	101	77	226	228	232	86	244	95	105	242	82	233	106	218	23	302	2925
61	264	248	224	99	97	93	239	81	230	220	83	243	92	107	219	28	297	2925
8	60	44	42	11	287	306	295	305	288	1	289	43	284	34	14	315	299	2925
265	317	281	283	314	38	19	30	20	37	324	36	282	41	291	311	26	10	2925
2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

It is a double-layer bordered magic square. Removing the external borders still we are left with lower order magic squares, for example of orders 14, 10, 6, etc.

Example 2.10. *Let's consider a magic square of order 18 given by*

mgc	18x18 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA ©IJT																	2925	
31	47	319	43	310	295	268	287	26	41	62	267	42	271	320	273	9	14	2925	
294	278	6	282	15	30	57	38	299	284	263	58	283	54	5	52	316	311	2925	
35	290	67	232	225	260	256	95	92	91	237	226	96	94	66	238	56	269	2925	
264	61	258	93	100	65	69	230	233	234	88	99	229	231	259	87	279	46	2925	
292	33	257	68	121	117	184	130	209	211	186	202	134	131	79	246	27	298	2925	
280	45	228	97	204	208	141	195	116	114	139	123	191	194	218	107	37	288	2925	
34	291	245	80	129	196	152	159	145	177	175	167	187	138	110	215	275	50	2925	
276	49	73	252	201	124	162	180	179	148	160	146	142	183	254	71	309	16	2925	
51	274	82	243	197	128	164	154	153	165	161	178	122	203	108	217	261	64	2925	
44	281	74	251	190	135	171	168	151	166	147	172	126	199	219	106	1	324	2925	
39	286	227	98	125	200	150	156	173	170	169	157	193	132	239	86	315	10	2925	
21	304	109	216	133	192	176	158	174	149	163	155	205	120	72	253	59	266	2925	
296	29	241	84	207	210	188	144	113	127	143	119	185	189	214	111	22	303	2925	
20	305	89	236	118	115	137	181	212	198	182	206	140	136	112	213	2	323	2925	
321	4	248	76	223	81	105	101	240	78	250	242	222	104	235	70	314	11	2925	
302	23	77	249	102	244	220	224	85	247	75	83	103	221	90	255	318	7	2925	
24	19	28	63	308	272	18	322	13	317	40	12	270	300	60	289	293	277	2925	
301	306	297	262	17	53	307	3	312	8	285	313	55	25	265	36	32	48	2925	
2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

*It is also a **double-layer bordered** magic square written in little different way. Here we don't have the blocks of order 2×2 . Removing the external borders still we are left with lower order magic squares, for example of orders 14, 10, 6, etc.*

Example 2.11. Let's consider a magic square of order 18 given by

mgc	18x18		https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	https://numbers-magic.com/	@IJTANEJA	©IJT	2925											
1	3	323	321	320	6	318	8	9	315	11	313	312	14	310	16	17	308	2925
324	322	2	4	5	319	7	317	316	10	314	12	13	311	15	309	19	306	2925
49	276	65	67	259	257	256	255	71	72	73	251	75	249	77	248	307	18	2925
275	50	260	258	66	68	69	70	254	253	252	74	250	76	79	246	305	20	2925
51	274	101	224	115	113	211	209	208	118	206	120	121	204	247	78	304	21	2925
273	52	223	102	210	212	114	116	117	207	119	205	123	202	245	80	22	303	2925
272	53	103	222	137	188	152	159	145	177	175	167	203	122	244	81	302	23	2925
54	271	221	104	187	138	162	180	179	148	160	146	201	124	243	82	24	301	2925
270	55	220	105	139	186	164	154	153	165	161	178	200	125	83	242	25	300	2925
56	269	219	106	185	140	171	168	151	166	147	172	126	199	84	241	299	26	2925
57	268	107	218	184	141	150	156	173	170	169	157	198	127	85	240	27	298	2925
267	58	108	217	182	143	176	158	174	149	163	155	128	197	239	86	297	28	2925
59	266	109	216	144	181	129	195	131	193	136	134	190	192	87	238	296	29	2925
265	60	111	214	142	183	196	130	194	132	189	191	135	133	237	88	30	295	2925
264	61	215	110	89	235	91	233	232	231	95	96	97	99	227	225	294	31	2925
262	63	213	112	236	90	234	92	93	94	230	229	228	226	98	100	32	293	2925
64	261	33	291	35	289	288	38	286	40	41	283	43	281	280	278	48	46	2925
62	263	292	34	290	36	37	287	39	285	284	42	282	44	45	47	277	279	2925
2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

It is also a **double-layer bordered** magic square written in little different way. Here the borders are of **cyclic-type**, i.e., of equal length in all the four sides, whereas the width is always same. Removing the external borders still we are left with lower order magic squares, for example of orders 14, 10, 6, etc.

For more details refer author's work [34, 35]

2.5 Striped Bordered Magic Squares

Example 2.12. *Let's consider a magic square of order 18 given by*

mgc	18x18		https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	https://numbers-magic.com/	@IJTANEJA	©IJT	2925											
31	47	319	43	310	295	268	287	26	41	62	267	42	271	320	273	9	14	2925
294	278	6	282	15	30	57	38	299	284	263	58	283	54	5	52	316	311	2925
35	290	67	232	225	260	256	95	92	91	237	226	96	94	66	238	56	269	2925
264	61	258	93	100	65	69	230	233	234	88	99	229	231	259	87	279	46	2925
292	33	257	68	121	117	184	130	209	211	186	202	134	131	79	246	27	298	2925
280	45	228	97	204	208	141	195	116	114	139	123	191	194	218	107	37	288	2925
34	291	245	80	129	196	154	171	147	178	173	152	187	138	110	215	275	50	2925
276	49	73	252	201	124	155	170	146	179	176	149	142	183	254	71	309	16	2925
51	274	82	243	197	128	169	156	177	148	150	175	122	203	108	217	261	64	2925
44	281	74	251	190	135	172	153	180	145	151	174	126	199	219	106	1	324	2925
39	286	227	98	125	200	165	159	164	157	167	163	193	132	239	86	315	10	2925
21	304	109	216	133	192	160	166	161	168	158	162	205	120	72	253	59	266	2925
296	29	241	84	207	210	188	144	113	127	143	119	185	189	214	111	22	303	2925
20	305	89	236	118	115	137	181	212	198	182	206	140	136	112	213	2	323	2925
321	4	248	76	223	81	105	101	240	78	250	242	222	104	235	70	314	11	2925
302	23	77	249	102	244	220	224	85	247	75	83	103	221	90	255	318	7	2925
24	19	28	63	308	272	18	322	13	317	40	12	270	300	60	289	293	277	2925
301	306	297	262	17	53	307	3	312	8	285	313	55	25	265	36	32	48	2925
2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

It is a double-layer striped magic square, where the width is always 2. The difference is only in the length. It composed magic rectangles.

Example 2.13. *Let's consider a magic square of order 18 given by*

mgc	18x18		https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	https://numbers-magic.com/	@IJTANEJA	©IJT	2925											
1	3	323	321	320	6	318	8	9	315	11	313	312	14	310	16	17	308	2925
324	322	2	4	5	319	7	317	316	10	314	12	13	311	15	309	19	306	2925
49	276	65	67	259	257	256	255	71	72	73	251	75	249	77	248	307	18	2925
275	50	260	258	66	68	69	70	254	253	252	74	250	76	79	246	305	20	2925
51	274	101	224	115	113	211	209	208	118	206	120	121	204	247	78	304	21	2925
273	52	223	102	210	212	114	116	117	207	119	205	123	202	245	80	22	303	2925
272	53	103	222	137	188	154	171	147	178	173	152	203	122	244	81	302	23	2925
54	271	221	104	187	138	155	170	146	179	176	149	201	124	243	82	24	301	2925
270	55	220	105	139	186	169	156	177	148	150	175	200	125	83	242	25	300	2925
56	269	219	106	185	140	172	153	180	145	151	174	126	199	84	241	299	26	2925
57	268	107	218	184	141	165	159	164	157	167	163	198	127	85	240	27	298	2925
267	58	108	217	182	143	160	166	161	168	158	162	128	197	239	86	297	28	2925
59	266	109	216	144	181	129	195	131	193	136	134	190	192	87	238	296	29	2925
265	60	111	214	142	183	196	130	194	132	189	191	135	133	237	88	30	295	2925
264	61	215	110	89	235	91	233	232	231	95	96	97	99	227	225	294	31	2925
262	63	213	112	236	90	234	92	93	94	230	229	228	226	98	100	32	293	2925
64	261	33	291	35	289	288	38	286	40	41	283	43	281	280	278	48	46	2925
62	263	292	34	290	36	37	287	39	285	284	42	282	44	45	47	277	279	2925
2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

It is also a double-layer striped magic square but written in cyclic way composed magic rectangles.

Example 2.14. *Let's consider a magic square of order 18 given by*

mgc	18x18 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/				https://numbers-magic.com/				@IJTANEJA		©IJT		2925						
177	180	146	147	143	182	192	133	213	112	234	91	83	242	52	273	302	23	2925	
148	145	179	178	138	187	135	190	212	113	236	89	245	80	303	22	265	60	2925	
181	188	139	142	184	141	197	128	208	117	104	221	76	249	58	267	36	289	2925	
144	137	186	183	185	140	194	131	120	205	93	232	68	257	13	312	27	298	2925	
126	129	191	198	195	136	132	193	110	215	97	228	253	72	284	41	32	293	2925	
199	196	134	127	130	189	125	200	201	124	227	98	251	74	278	47	25	300	2925	
203	109	211	206	118	123	214	116	115	210	217	108	77	248	15	310	61	264	2925	
122	216	114	119	207	202	111	209	121	204	219	106	239	86	304	21	261	64	2925	
92	99	225	230	105	90	224	222	107	231	96	229	240	85	40	285	283	42	2925	
233	226	100	95	220	235	101	103	218	94	102	223	84	241	19	306	288	37	2925	
247	256	250	87	65	70	88	246	67	71	244	259	82	243	319	6	321	4	2925	
78	69	75	238	260	255	237	79	258	254	81	66	252	73	274	51	287	38	2925	
149	175	164	173	153	171	170	156	168	158	159	165	151	163	299	26	31	294	2925	
176	150	161	152	172	154	155	169	157	167	166	160	174	162	17	308	56	269	2925	
324	322	271	12	314	279	62	5	301	63	7	39	16	311	272	270	49	8	2925	
1	3	54	313	11	46	263	320	24	262	318	286	309	14	53	55	276	317	2925	
266	307	45	57	275	29	315	20	35	277	291	323	9	292	282	44	28	30	2925	
59	18	280	268	50	296	10	305	290	48	34	2	316	33	43	281	297	295	2925	
2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

It is also a double-layer striped magic square but written in corner-type magic square.

Example 2.15. *Let's consider a magic square of order 18 given by*

mgc	18x18 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/						https://numbers-magic.com/						@IJTANEJA		©IJT		2925		
1	11	3	9	8	7	277	287	279	285	284	283	193	203	195	201	200	199	2925	
12	2	10	4	5	6	288	278	286	280	281	282	204	194	202	196	197	198	2925	
169	179	177	171	176	175	289	299	291	297	296	295	13	23	15	20	21	19	2925	
180	170	172	178	173	174	300	290	298	292	293	294	24	14	22	17	16	18	2925	
49	59	51	57	56	55	205	215	207	213	212	211	227	217	219	225	224	223	2925	
60	50	58	52	53	54	216	206	214	208	209	210	218	228	226	220	221	222	2925	
181	191	183	189	188	187	229	239	231	237	236	235	61	71	63	69	68	67	2925	
192	182	190	184	185	186	240	230	238	232	233	234	72	62	70	64	65	66	2925	
241	251	243	249	248	247	157	167	159	164	165	163	73	83	75	81	80	79	2925	
252	242	250	244	245	246	168	158	166	161	160	162	84	74	82	76	77	78	2925	
253	263	255	261	260	259	95	85	87	93	92	91	133	143	135	141	140	139	2925	
264	254	262	256	257	258	86	96	94	88	89	90	144	134	142	136	137	138	2925	
97	107	99	104	105	103	109	119	111	117	116	115	275	265	267	273	272	271	2925	
108	98	106	101	100	102	120	110	118	112	113	114	266	276	274	268	269	270	2925	
301	311	303	307	308	309	25	35	27	33	32	31	145	155	153	147	152	151	2925	
312	302	310	306	305	304	36	26	34	28	29	30	156	146	148	154	149	150	2925	
121	131	123	129	128	127	37	47	39	45	44	43	313	323	315	321	320	319	2925	
132	122	130	124	125	126	48	38	46	40	41	42	324	314	322	316	317	318	2925	
2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

*It is a **striped** magic square made of equal width and length magic rectangles.*

For more details refer author's work [40, 41, 42, 43, 44, 45, 46].

2.6 Different Designed Magic Squares

Example 2.16. *Let's consider a magic square of order 18 given by*

mgc	18x18 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/						https://numbers-magic.com/						@IJTANEJA		©IJT		2925	
6	320	318	324	3	4	302	300	21	306	22	24	39	40	288	282	42	284	2925
5	319	7	1	322	321	20	35	292	29	294	305	286	285	37	43	41	283	2925
9	316	17	310	11	312	26	30	293	36	291	299	53	274	47	276	45	280	2925
323	2	12	311	18	309	28	296	31	290	33	297	48	275	54	273	279	46	2925
315	10	314	13	308	15	298	289	34	295	32	27	278	49	272	51	287	38	2925
317	8	307	16	313	14	301	25	304	19	303	23	271	52	277	50	281	44	2925
194	192	129	198	130	132	176	174	147	180	148	150	266	264	57	270	58	60	2925
128	143	184	137	186	197	146	161	166	155	168	179	56	71	256	65	258	269	2925
134	138	185	144	183	191	152	156	167	162	165	173	62	66	257	72	255	263	2925
136	188	139	182	141	189	154	170	157	164	159	171	64	260	67	254	69	261	2925
190	181	142	187	140	135	172	163	160	169	158	153	262	253	70	259	68	63	2925
193	133	196	127	195	131	175	151	178	145	177	149	265	61	268	55	267	59	2925
209	116	125	202	119	204	230	228	93	234	94	96	89	238	83	240	245	80	2925
215	110	120	203	126	201	92	107	220	101	222	233	84	239	90	237	243	82	2925
207	118	206	121	200	123	98	102	221	108	219	227	242	85	236	87	251	74	2925
117	208	199	124	205	122	100	224	103	218	105	225	235	88	241	86	81	244	2925
114	212	210	216	112	111	226	217	106	223	104	99	76	75	252	246	78	248	2925
113	211	115	109	213	214	229	97	232	91	231	95	249	250	73	79	77	247	2925
2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

It is mixed-type symmetric designed magic square.

For more details refer author's work [6, 7, 8, 10, 53].

2.7 Magic Rectangles and Magic Squares

Example 2.17. *Let's consider a magic square of order 18 given by*

mgc	18x18 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/			https://numbers-magic.com/			@IJTANEJA	©IJT	2925																																			
13	6	315	313	317	310	1	3	16	5	321	323	14	318	41	286	288	35	2925																										
314	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>297</td><td>22</td><td>300</td><td>23</td><td>26</td><td>307</td><td>301</td><td>20</td><td>17</td><td>304</td><td>306</td><td>27</td><td>11</td> </tr> <tr> <td>28</td><td>303</td><td>25</td><td>302</td><td>299</td><td>18</td><td>24</td><td>305</td><td>308</td><td>21</td><td>19</td><td>298</td><td>9</td> </tr> </table>												297	22	300	23	26	307	301	20	17	304	306	27	11	28	303	25	302	299	18	24	305	308	21	19	298	9	287	50	275	38	2925	
297													22	300	23	26	307	301	20	17	304	306	27	11																				
28	303	25	302	299	18	24	305	308	21	19	298	9																																
316	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>7</td><td>319</td><td>10</td><td>12</td><td>8</td><td>15</td><td>324</td><td>322</td><td>309</td><td>320</td><td>4</td><td>2</td><td>311</td><td>312</td> </tr> </table>												7	319	10	12	8	15	324	322	309	320	4	2	311	312	285	272	53	40	2925													
7													319	10	12	8	15	324	322	309	320	4	2	311	312																			
97	230	232	91	115	113	211	209	208	118	206	120	121	204	289	51	274	36	2925																										
90	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>213</td><td>112</td><td>235</td><td>210</td><td>212</td><td>114</td><td>116</td><td>117</td><td>207</td><td>119</td><td>205</td><td>123</td><td>202</td> </tr> </table>												213	112	235	210	212	114	116	117	207	119	205	123	202	282	54	271	43	2925														
213													112	235	210	212	114	116	117	207	119	205	123	202																				
231	106	219	94	137	188	150	174	147	180	148	176	203	122	29	279	46	296	2925																										
229	216	109	96	187	138	179	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>161</td><td>166</td><td>155</td><td>168</td><td>146</td><td>201</td><td>124</td> </tr> </table>		161	166	155	168	146	201	124	31	273	52	294	2925																								
161	166	155	168	146	201	124																																						
233	222	103	92	139	186	173	156	167	162	165	152	200	125	44	48	277	281	2925																										
226	111	214	99	185	140	171	170	157	164	159	154	126	199	33	269	56	292	2925																										
85	223	102	240	184	141	153	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>163</td><td>160</td><td>169</td><td>158</td><td>172</td><td>198</td><td>127</td> </tr> </table>		163	160	169	158	172	198	127	293	276	49	32	2925																								
163	160	169	158	172	198	127																																						
87	217	108	238	182	143	149	151	178	145	177	175	128	197	295	278	47	30	2925																										
100	104	221	225	144	181	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>129</td><td>195</td><td>131</td><td>193</td><td>136</td><td>134</td><td>190</td><td>192</td> </tr> </table>		129	195	131	193	136	134	190	192	42	55	270	283	2925																								
129	195	131	193	136	134			190	192																																			
89	101	224	236	142	183	196	130	194	132	189	191	135	133	290	39	37	284	2925																										
237	220	105	88	69	62	259	257	261	254	57	59	72	61	265	267	70	262	2925																										
239	107	218	86	258	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>241</td><td>78</td><td>244</td><td>83</td><td>82</td><td>251</td><td>245</td><td>76</td><td>73</td><td>248</td><td>79</td><td>250</td><td>67</td> </tr> <tr> <td>84</td><td>247</td><td>81</td><td>242</td><td>243</td><td>74</td><td>80</td><td>249</td><td>252</td><td>77</td><td>246</td><td>75</td><td>65</td> </tr> </table>												241	78	244	83	82	251	245	76	73	248	79	250	67	84	247	81	242	243	74	80	249	252	77	246	75	65	67	2925
241	78	244	83	82													251	245	76	73	248	79	250	67																				
84	247	81	242	243	74	80	249	252	77	246	75	65																																
98	110	215	227	260	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>84</td><td>247</td><td>81</td><td>242</td><td>243</td><td>74</td><td>80</td><td>249</td><td>252</td><td>77</td><td>246</td><td>75</td><td>65</td> </tr> </table>												84	247	81	242	243	74	80	249	252	77	246	75	65	65	2925													
84	247	81	242	243													74	80	249	252	77	246	75	65																				
234	95	93	228	63	263	66	68	64	71	268	266	253	264	60	58	255	256	2925																										
2925 2925 2925 2925 2925 2925 2925 2925 2925 2925 2925 2925 2925 2925 2925 2925 2925 2925																		2925																										

It is mixed-type magic square composed of magic squares and bordered magic rectangles.

Example 2.18. *Let's consider a magic square of order 18 given by*

mgc	18x18 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA ©IJT																	2925
5	3	314	2	324	318	319	312	8	18	16	313	4	311	19	308	316	15	2925
20	27	36	297	304	30	31	301	299	23	296	293	25	292	22	290	34	305	2925
315	298	289	28	21	295	294	24	26	302	29	32	300	33	303	35	291	10	2925
310	322	11	323	1	7	6	13	317	307	309	12	321	14	306	17	9	320	2925
89	243	237	242	78	77	86	231	235	96	98	238	249	241	75	74	91	245	2925
232	100	218	109	116	213	208	219	120	224	108	110	211	103	212	115	214	93	2925
85	119	137	193	196	190	121	197	133	202	191	200	127	138	126	124	206	240	2925
230	207	189	147	142	148	145	184	140	174	173	150	186	182	179	136	118	95	2925
97	221	195	181	160	172	164	167	166	155	154	163	168	156	144	130	104	228	2925
246	223	131	176	165	153	161	158	159	170	171	162	157	169	149	194	102	79	2925
233	220	122	146	183	177	180	141	185	151	152	175	139	143	178	203	105	92	2925
252	99	201	132	129	135	204	128	192	123	134	125	198	187	199	188	226	73	2925
81	111	107	216	209	112	117	106	205	101	217	215	114	222	113	210	225	244	2925
80	82	88	83	247	248	239	94	90	229	227	87	76	84	250	251	234	236	2925
41	39	278	275	288	282	283	276	44	54	52	277	40	272	55	38	280	51	2925
56	254	72	261	63	66	67	265	263	70	260	257	61	256	59	268	58	269	2925
279	71	253	64	262	259	258	60	62	255	65	68	264	69	266	57	267	46	2925
274	286	47	50	37	43	42	49	281	271	273	48	285	53	270	287	45	284	2925
2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

It is mixed-type magic square composed of bordered magic rectangles.

Example 2.19. *Let's consider a magic square of order 18 given by*

mgc	18x18 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/				https://numbers-magic.com/				@IJTANEJA	©IJT	2925								
87	240	81	242	7	313	316	6	8	321	10	2	322	320	95	232	89	234	2925	
82	241	88	239	324	307	20	16	311	13	310	17	306	1	90	233	96	231	2925	
244	83	238	85	314	18	305	309	14	312	15	308	19	11	236	91	230	93	2925	
237	86	243	84	5	12	9	319	317	4	315	323	3	318	229	94	235	92	2925	
67	264	254	65	203	196	198	210	130	128	126	116	114	204	27	304	294	25	2925	
253	247	78	72	125	137	190	131	192	145	182	139	184	200	293	287	38	32	2925	
256	80	245	69	123	132	191	138	189	140	183	146	181	202	296	40	285	29	2925	
66	76	249	259	119	194	133	188	135	186	141	180	143	206	26	36	289	299	2925	
68	251	74	257	113	187	136	193	134	179	144	185	142	212	28	291	34	297	2925	
261	73	252	64	201	153	174	147	176	161	166	155	168	124	301	33	292	24	2925	
70	250	75	255	205	148	175	154	173	156	167	162	165	120	30	290	35	295	2925	
62	77	248	263	207	178	149	172	151	170	157	164	159	118	22	37	288	303	2925	
262	246	79	63	208	171	152	177	150	163	160	169	158	117	302	286	39	23	2925	
260	61	71	258	121	129	127	115	195	197	199	209	211	122	300	21	31	298	2925	
111	216	105	218	47	273	276	46	48	281	50	42	282	280	103	224	97	226	2925	
106	217	112	215	284	267	60	56	271	53	270	57	266	41	98	225	104	223	2925	
220	107	214	109	274	58	265	269	54	272	55	268	59	51	228	99	222	101	2925	
213	110	219	108	45	52	49	279	277	44	275	283	43	278	221	102	227	100	2925	
2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

It is mixed-type magic square composed of magic squares and bordered magic rectangles.

For more details refer author's work [6, 7, 8, 10, 53]

2.8 Triple-Layer Magic Squares

Example 2.20. *Let's consider a magic square of order 18 given by*

mgc	18x18 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/			https://numbers-magic.com/			@IJTANEJA	©IJT	2925									
274	279	272	247	252	245	85	90	83	67	72	65	13	18	11	283	288	281	2925
273	275	277	246	248	250	84	86	88	66	68	70	12	14	16	282	284	286	2925
278	271	276	251	244	249	89	82	87	71	64	69	17	10	15	287	280	285	2925
58	63	56	150	145	152	195	190	197	96	91	98	213	208	215	265	270	263	2925
57	59	61	151	149	147	196	194	192	97	95	93	214	212	210	264	266	268	2925
62	55	60	146	153	148	191	198	193	92	99	94	209	216	211	269	262	267	2925
4	9	2	105	100	107	204	199	206	159	154	161	186	181	188	319	324	317	2925
3	5	7	106	104	102	205	203	201	160	158	156	187	185	183	318	320	322	2925
8	1	6	101	108	103	200	207	202	155	162	157	182	189	184	323	316	321	2925
292	297	290	231	226	233	114	109	116	177	172	179	132	127	134	31	36	29	2925
291	293	295	232	230	228	115	113	111	178	176	174	133	131	129	30	32	34	2925
296	289	294	227	234	229	110	117	112	173	180	175	128	135	130	35	28	33	2925
301	306	299	168	163	170	141	136	143	222	217	224	123	118	125	22	27	20	2925
300	302	304	169	167	165	142	140	138	223	221	219	124	122	120	21	23	25	2925
305	298	303	164	171	166	137	144	139	218	225	220	119	126	121	26	19	24	2925
40	45	38	76	81	74	238	243	236	256	261	254	310	315	308	49	54	47	2925
39	41	43	75	77	79	237	239	241	255	257	259	309	311	313	48	50	52	2925
44	37	42	80	73	78	242	235	240	260	253	258	314	307	312	53	46	51	2925
2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

*It is a **triple-layer bordered** magic square. It is composed of magic squares of order 3 in such a way that if we remove external border still we are left with magic squares of lower orders.*

Example 2.21. *Let's consider a magic square of order 18 given by*

mgc	18x18 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/			https://numbers-magic.com/			@IJTANEJA	©IJT	2925										
274	279	272	247	252	245	85	90	83	67	72	65	13	18	11	283	288	281	2925	
273	275	277	246	248	250	84	86	88	66	68	70	12	14	16	282	284	286	2925	
278	271	276	251	244	249	89	82	87	71	64	69	17	10	15	287	280	285	2925	
58	63	56	230	228	93	234	94	96	212	210	111	216	112	114	265	270	263	2925	
57	59	61	92	107	220	101	222	233	110	125	202	119	204	215	264	266	268	2925	
62	55	60	98	102	221	108	219	227	116	120	203	126	201	209	269	262	267	2925	
4	9	2	100	224	103	218	105	225	118	206	121	200	123	207	319	324	317	2925	
3	5	7	226	217	106	223	104	99	208	199	124	205	122	117	318	320	322	2925	
8	1	6	229	97	232	91	231	95	211	115	214	109	213	113	323	316	321	2925	
292	297	290	176	174	147	180	148	150	194	192	129	198	130	132	31	36	29	2925	
291	293	295	146	161	166	155	168	179	128	143	184	137	186	197	30	32	34	2925	
296	289	294	152	156	167	162	165	173	134	138	185	144	183	191	35	28	33	2925	
301	306	299	154	170	157	164	159	171	136	188	139	182	141	189	22	27	20	2925	
300	302	304	172	163	160	169	158	153	190	181	142	187	140	135	21	23	25	2925	
305	298	303	175	151	178	145	177	149	193	133	196	127	195	131	26	19	24	2925	
40	45	38	76	81	74	238	243	236	256	261	254	310	315	308	49	54	47	2925	
39	41	43	75	77	79	237	239	241	255	257	259	309	311	313	48	50	52	2925	
44	37	42	80	73	78	242	235	240	260	253	258	314	307	312	53	46	51	2925	
2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

It is a triple-layer bordered magic square. embedded with four equal sums single-layer magic squares of order 6.

Example 2.22. *Let's consider a magic square of order 18 given by*

mgc	18x18			https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	https://numbers-magic.com/	@IJTANEJA	©IJT	2925											
274	279	272	247	252	245	85	90	83	67	72	65	13	18	11	283	288	281	2925	
273	275	277	246	248	250	84	86	88	66	68	70	12	14	16	282	284	286	2925	
278	271	276	251	244	249	89	82	87	71	64	69	17	10	15	287	280	285	2925	
58	63	56	94	91	233	232	95	229	228	98	99	102	224	225	265	270	263	2925	
57	59	61	231	234	92	93	230	96	97	227	226	223	101	100	264	266	268	2925	
62	55	60	127	198	138	132	192	194	181	143	183	137	103	222	269	262	267	2925	
4	9	2	197	128	135	176	174	147	180	148	150	190	221	104	319	324	317	2925	
3	5	7	196	129	136	146	161	166	155	168	179	189	220	105	318	320	322	2925	
8	1	6	130	195	141	152	156	167	162	165	173	184	106	219	323	316	321	2925	
292	297	290	123	202	191	154	170	157	164	159	171	134	107	218	31	36	29	2925	
291	293	295	201	124	186	172	163	160	169	158	153	139	217	108	30	32	34	2925	
296	289	294	200	125	185	175	151	178	145	177	149	140	216	109	35	28	33	2925	
301	306	299	126	199	188	193	133	131	144	182	142	187	110	215	22	27	20	2925	
300	302	304	205	204	122	119	115	209	208	118	212	213	111	114	21	23	25	2925	
305	298	303	120	121	203	206	210	116	117	207	113	112	214	211	26	19	24	2925	
40	45	38	76	81	74	238	243	236	256	261	254	310	315	308	49	54	47	2925	
39	41	43	75	77	79	237	239	241	255	257	259	309	311	313	48	50	52	2925	
44	37	42	80	73	78	242	235	240	260	253	258	314	307	312	53	46	51	2925	
2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

It is a triple-layer bordered magic square. embedded with a mixed-type magic square of order 12.

Example 2.23. *Let's consider a magic square of order 18 given by*

mgc	18x18			https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	https://numbers-magic.com/	@IJTANEJA	©IJT	2925										
274	279	272	247	252	245	85	90	83	67	72	65	13	18	11	283	288	281	2925
273	275	277	246	248	250	84	86	88	66	68	70	12	14	16	282	284	286	2925
278	271	276	251	244	249	89	82	87	71	64	69	17	10	15	287	280	285	2925
58	63	56	161	166	155	168	178	147	181	144	204	121	226	99	265	270	263	2925
57	59	61	156	167	162	165	177	148	142	183	207	118	221	104	264	266	268	2925
62	55	60	170	157	164	159	146	179	140	185	126	199	219	106	269	262	267	2925
4	9	2	163	160	169	158	150	175	135	190	115	210	105	220	319	324	317	2925
3	5	7	153	145	176	154	173	174	137	188	125	200	213	112	318	320	322	2925
8	1	6	172	180	149	171	151	152	186	139	212	113	108	217	323	316	321	2925
292	297	290	132	189	131	143	191	184	192	138	114	211	223	102	31	36	29	2925
291	293	295	193	136	194	182	134	141	187	133	202	123	109	216	30	32	34	2925
296	289	294	127	117	203	197	195	209	205	129	119	124	233	92	35	28	33	2925
301	306	299	198	208	122	128	130	116	120	196	201	206	98	227	22	27	20	2925
300	302	304	111	91	224	107	215	94	96	228	232	222	100	230	21	23	25	2925
305	298	303	214	234	101	218	110	231	229	97	93	103	95	225	26	19	24	2925
40	45	38	76	81	74	238	243	236	256	261	254	310	315	308	49	54	47	2925
39	41	43	75	77	79	237	239	241	255	257	259	309	311	313	48	50	52	2925
44	37	42	80	73	78	242	235	240	260	253	258	314	307	312	53	46	51	2925
2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

It is a triple-layer bordered magic square. embedded with a cornered magic square of order 12.

2.9 Palindromic-Number Entries Magic Square

Example 2.24. *Let's consider a magic square of order 18 with palindromic entries:*

mgc	18x18 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA ©IJT																	970020	
42524	41214	44344	45454	46264	43534	92529	91219	94349	95459	96269	93539	22522	21212	24342	25452	26262	23532	970020	
41114	43334	46564	44544	45154	42624	91119	93339	96569	94549	95159	92629	21112	23332	26562	24542	25152	22622	970020	
43134	46364	45354	42224	44644	41614	93139	96369	95359	92229	94649	91619	23132	26362	25352	22222	24642	21612	970020	
44244	42424	41314	46464	43634	45254	94249	92429	91319	96469	93639	95259	24242	22422	21312	26462	23632	25252	970020	
45654	44444	42324	43234	41514	46164	95659	94449	92329	93239	91519	96169	25652	24442	22322	23232	21512	26162	970020	
46664	45554	43434	41414	42124	44144	96669	95559	93439	91419	92129	94149	26662	25552	23432	21412	22122	24142	970020	
32523	31213	34343	35453	36263	33533	52525	51215	54345	55455	56265	53535	72527	71217	74347	75457	76267	73537	970020	
31113	33333	36563	34543	35153	32623	51115	53335	56565	54545	55155	52625	71117	73337	76567	74547	75157	72627	970020	
33133	36363	35353	32223	34643	31613	53135	56365	55355	52225	54645	51615	73137	76367	75357	72227	74647	71617	970020	
34243	32423	31313	36463	33633	35253	54245	52425	51315	56465	53635	55255	74247	72427	71317	76467	73637	75257	970020	
35653	34443	32323	33233	31513	36163	55655	54445	52325	53235	51515	56165	75657	74447	72327	73237	71517	76167	970020	
36663	35553	33433	31413	32123	34143	56665	55555	53435	51415	52125	54145	76667	75557	73437	71417	72127	74147	970020	
82528	81218	84348	85458	86268	83538	12521	11211	14341	15451	16261	13531	62526	61216	64346	65456	66266	63536	970020	
81118	83338	86568	84548	85158	82628	11111	13331	16561	14541	15151	12621	61116	63336	66566	64546	65156	62626	970020	
83138	86368	85358	82228	84648	81618	13131	16361	15351	12221	14641	11611	63136	66366	65356	62226	64646	61616	970020	
84248	82428	81318	86468	83638	85258	14241	12421	11311	16461	13631	15251	64246	62426	61316	66466	63636	65256	970020	
85658	84448	82328	83238	81518	86168	15651	14441	12321	13231	11511	16161	65656	64446	62326	63236	61516	66166	970020	
86668	85558	83438	81418	82128	84148	16661	15551	13431	11411	12121	14141	66666	65556	63436	61416	62126	64146	970020	
970020	970020	970020	970020	970020	970020	970020	970020	970020	970020	970020	970020	970020	970020	970020	970020	970020	970020	970020	970020

It is composed of equal sums magic square of order 6 having palindromic number entries.

For more details refer author's work ??

3 Different Aspects of Magic Squares

3.1 Perfect Square Entries Sum

Below are five different magic squares of order 18 resulting in **uniformity**, **Pythagorean triples** and **minimum perfect square sum** properties. Out of these five, three of them are with **fraction numbers** entries.

3.1.1 Uniformity Property

Example 3.1. A *block-wise* magic square of order 18 for consecutive odd numbers entries $\{1, 3, 5, \dots, 645, 647\}$ is given by

mgc	18x18 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/						https://numbers-magic.com/						@IJTANEJA	©IJT	5832				
1	613	611	577	35	107	3	615	609	579	33	105	5	617	607	581	31	103	5832	
539	143	503	145	181	433	537	141	501	147	183	435	535	139	499	149	185	437	5832	
431	397	253	287	359	217	429	399	255	285	357	219	427	401	257	283	355	221	5832	
323	251	361	395	289	325	321	249	363	393	291	327	319	247	365	391	293	329	5832	
109	467	179	469	505	215	111	465	177	471	507	213	113	463	175	473	509	211	5832	
541	73	37	71	575	647	543	75	39	69	573	645	545	77	41	67	571	643	5832	
7	619	605	583	29	101	9	621	603	585	27	99	11	623	601	587	25	97	5832	
533	137	497	151	187	439	531	135	495	153	189	441	529	133	493	155	191	443	5832	
425	403	259	281	353	223	423	405	261	279	351	225	421	407	263	277	349	227	5832	
317	245	367	389	295	331	315	243	369	387	297	333	313	241	371	385	299	335	5832	
115	461	173	475	511	209	117	459	171	477	513	207	119	457	169	479	515	205	5832	
547	79	43	65	569	641	549	81	45	63	567	639	551	83	47	61	565	637	5832	
13	625	599	589	23	95	15	627	597	591	21	93	17	629	595	593	19	91	5832	
527	131	491	157	193	445	525	129	489	159	195	447	523	127	487	161	197	449	5832	
419	409	265	275	347	229	417	411	267	273	345	231	415	413	269	271	343	233	5832	
311	239	373	383	301	337	309	237	375	381	303	339	307	235	377	379	305	341	5832	
121	455	167	481	517	203	123	453	165	483	519	201	125	451	163	485	521	199	5832	
553	85	49	59	563	635	555	87	51	57	561	633	557	89	53	55	559	631	5832	
5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832

Example 3.2. A *block-wise* magic square of order 18 for consecutive fraction numbers entries $\{325/2, 327/2, \dots, 967/2, 971/2\}$ is given by

mgc	18x18	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	https://numbers-magic.com/	@IJTANEJA	©IJT	5832												
162.5	468.5	467.5	450.5	179.5	215.5	163.5	469.5	466.5	451.5	178.5	214.5	164.5	470.5	465.5	452.5	177.5	213.5	5832
431.5	233.5	413.5	234.5	252.5	378.5	430.5	232.5	412.5	235.5	253.5	379.5	429.5	231.5	411.5	236.5	254.5	380.5	5832
377.5	360.5	288.5	305.5	341.5	270.5	376.5	361.5	289.5	304.5	340.5	271.5	375.5	362.5	290.5	303.5	339.5	272.5	5832
323.5	287.5	342.5	359.5	306.5	324.5	322.5	286.5	343.5	358.5	307.5	325.5	321.5	285.5	344.5	357.5	308.5	326.5	5832
216.5	395.5	251.5	396.5	414.5	269.5	217.5	394.5	250.5	397.5	415.5	268.5	218.5	393.5	249.5	398.5	416.5	267.5	5832
432.5	198.5	180.5	197.5	449.5	485.5	433.5	199.5	181.5	196.5	448.5	484.5	434.5	200.5	182.5	195.5	447.5	483.5	5832
165.5	471.5	464.5	453.5	176.5	212.5	166.5	472.5	463.5	454.5	175.5	211.5	167.5	473.5	462.5	455.5	174.5	210.5	5832
428.5	230.5	410.5	237.5	255.5	381.5	427.5	229.5	409.5	238.5	256.5	382.5	426.5	228.5	408.5	239.5	257.5	383.5	5832
374.5	363.5	291.5	302.5	338.5	273.5	373.5	364.5	292.5	301.5	337.5	274.5	372.5	365.5	293.5	300.5	336.5	275.5	5832
320.5	284.5	345.5	356.5	309.5	327.5	319.5	283.5	346.5	355.5	310.5	328.5	318.5	282.5	347.5	354.5	311.5	329.5	5832
219.5	392.5	248.5	399.5	417.5	266.5	220.5	391.5	247.5	400.5	418.5	265.5	221.5	390.5	246.5	401.5	419.5	264.5	5832
435.5	201.5	183.5	194.5	446.5	482.5	436.5	202.5	184.5	193.5	445.5	481.5	437.5	203.5	185.5	192.5	444.5	480.5	5832
168.5	474.5	461.5	456.5	173.5	209.5	169.5	475.5	460.5	457.5	172.5	208.5	170.5	476.5	459.5	458.5	171.5	207.5	5832
425.5	227.5	407.5	240.5	258.5	384.5	424.5	226.5	406.5	241.5	259.5	385.5	423.5	225.5	405.5	242.5	260.5	386.5	5832
371.5	366.5	294.5	299.5	335.5	276.5	370.5	367.5	295.5	298.5	334.5	277.5	369.5	368.5	296.5	297.5	333.5	278.5	5832
317.5	281.5	348.5	353.5	312.5	330.5	316.5	280.5	349.5	352.5	313.5	331.5	315.5	279.5	350.5	351.5	314.5	332.5	5832
222.5	389.5	245.5	402.5	420.5	263.5	223.5	388.5	244.5	403.5	421.5	262.5	224.5	387.5	243.5	404.5	422.5	261.5	5832
438.5	204.5	186.5	191.5	443.5	479.5	439.5	205.5	187.5	190.5	442.5	478.5	440.5	206.5	188.5	189.5	441.5	477.5	5832
5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832	5832

In both the Examples 3.1 and 3.2, the magic sums are equal. The blocks of order 6 are magic squares with equal magic sums. See below the details:

$$S_{18 \times 18} = 5832 = 18^3; \quad T_{324} := 104976 = 324^2 = 18^4;$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} = 1944; \quad T_{36} := 11664 = 108^2.$$

The Examples ?? and ?? also satisfy the **uniformity property**, i.e., $\langle 18, 18^2, 18^3, 18^4 \rangle$.

3.1.2 Pythagorean Triple

Example 3.3. A *block-wise magic square* of order 18 for consecutive odd numbers entries $\{77, 79, \dots, 721, 723\}$ is given by

mgc	18x18 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/						https://numbers-magic.com/						@IJTANEJA	©IJT	7200			
77	689	687	653	111	183	79	691	685	655	109	181	81	693	683	657	107	179	7200
615	219	579	221	257	509	613	217	577	223	259	511	611	215	575	225	261	513	7200
507	473	329	363	435	293	505	475	331	361	433	295	503	477	333	359	431	297	7200
399	327	437	471	365	401	397	325	439	469	367	403	395	323	441	467	369	405	7200
185	543	255	545	581	291	187	541	253	547	583	289	189	539	251	549	585	287	7200
617	149	113	147	651	723	619	151	115	145	649	721	621	153	117	143	647	719	7200
83	695	681	659	105	177	85	697	679	661	103	175	87	699	677	663	101	173	7200
609	213	573	227	263	515	607	211	571	229	265	517	605	209	569	231	267	519	7200
501	479	335	357	429	299	499	481	337	355	427	301	497	483	339	353	425	303	7200
393	321	443	465	371	407	391	319	445	463	373	409	389	317	447	461	375	411	7200
191	537	249	551	587	285	193	535	247	553	589	283	195	533	245	555	591	281	7200
623	155	119	141	645	717	625	157	121	139	643	715	627	159	123	137	641	713	7200
89	701	675	665	99	171	91	703	673	667	97	169	93	705	671	669	95	167	7200
603	207	567	233	269	521	601	205	565	235	271	523	599	203	563	237	273	525	7200
495	485	341	351	423	305	493	487	343	349	421	307	491	489	345	347	419	309	7200
387	315	449	459	377	413	385	313	451	457	379	415	383	311	453	455	381	417	7200
197	531	243	557	593	279	199	529	241	559	595	277	201	527	239	561	597	275	7200
629	161	125	135	639	711	631	163	127	133	637	709	633	165	129	131	635	707	7200
7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200

Example 3.4. A *block-wise magic square* of order 18 for consecutive fraction numbers entries $\{477/2, 479/2, \dots, 1121/2, 1123/2\}$ is given by

mgc	18x18	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	https://numbers-magic.com/	@IJTANEJA	©IJT	7200												
238.5	544.5	543.5	526.5	255.5	291.5	239.5	545.5	542.5	527.5	254.5	290.5	240.5	546.5	541.5	528.5	253.5	289.5	7200
507.5	309.5	489.5	310.5	328.5	454.5	506.5	308.5	488.5	311.5	329.5	455.5	505.5	307.5	487.5	312.5	330.5	456.5	7200
453.5	436.5	364.5	381.5	417.5	346.5	452.5	437.5	365.5	380.5	416.5	347.5	451.5	438.5	366.5	379.5	415.5	348.5	7200
399.5	363.5	418.5	435.5	382.5	400.5	398.5	362.5	419.5	434.5	383.5	401.5	397.5	361.5	420.5	433.5	384.5	402.5	7200
292.5	471.5	327.5	472.5	490.5	345.5	293.5	470.5	326.5	473.5	491.5	344.5	294.5	469.5	325.5	474.5	492.5	343.5	7200
508.5	274.5	256.5	273.5	525.5	561.5	509.5	275.5	257.5	272.5	524.5	560.5	510.5	276.5	258.5	271.5	523.5	559.5	7200
241.5	547.5	540.5	529.5	252.5	288.5	242.5	548.5	539.5	530.5	251.5	287.5	243.5	549.5	538.5	531.5	250.5	286.5	7200
504.5	306.5	486.5	313.5	331.5	457.5	503.5	305.5	485.5	314.5	332.5	458.5	502.5	304.5	484.5	315.5	333.5	459.5	7200
450.5	439.5	367.5	378.5	414.5	349.5	449.5	440.5	368.5	377.5	413.5	350.5	448.5	441.5	369.5	376.5	412.5	351.5	7200
396.5	360.5	421.5	432.5	385.5	403.5	395.5	359.5	422.5	431.5	386.5	404.5	394.5	358.5	423.5	430.5	387.5	405.5	7200
295.5	468.5	324.5	475.5	493.5	342.5	296.5	467.5	323.5	476.5	494.5	341.5	297.5	466.5	322.5	477.5	495.5	340.5	7200
511.5	277.5	259.5	270.5	522.5	558.5	512.5	278.5	260.5	269.5	521.5	557.5	513.5	279.5	261.5	268.5	520.5	556.5	7200
244.5	550.5	537.5	532.5	249.5	285.5	245.5	551.5	536.5	533.5	248.5	284.5	246.5	552.5	535.5	534.5	247.5	283.5	7200
501.5	303.5	483.5	316.5	334.5	460.5	500.5	302.5	482.5	317.5	335.5	461.5	499.5	301.5	481.5	318.5	336.5	462.5	7200
447.5	442.5	370.5	375.5	411.5	352.5	446.5	443.5	371.5	374.5	410.5	353.5	445.5	444.5	372.5	373.5	409.5	354.5	7200
393.5	357.5	424.5	429.5	388.5	406.5	392.5	356.5	425.5	428.5	389.5	407.5	391.5	355.5	426.5	427.5	390.5	408.5	7200
298.5	465.5	321.5	478.5	496.5	339.5	299.5	464.5	320.5	479.5	497.5	338.5	300.5	463.5	319.5	480.5	498.5	337.5	7200
514.5	280.5	262.5	267.5	519.5	555.5	515.5	281.5	263.5	266.5	518.5	554.5	516.5	282.5	264.5	265.5	517.5	553.5	7200
7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200	7200

The **block-wise** magic squares of order 18 given in Examples 3.3 and 3.4 are respectively with equal magic sums. The blocks of order 6 are magic squares with equal magic sums. See below the details:

$$S_{18 \times 18} = 7200; \quad T_{324} := 18 \times 7200 = 129600 = 360^2;$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} = 2400; \quad T_{36} := 6 \times 2400 = 14400 = 120^2.$$

Both the Examples 3.3 and 3.4 are generated by **Pythagorean triple (38,360,362)**, i.e., $38^2 + 360^2 = 362^2$ with least possible sum of entries resulting in a **perfect square**.

3.1.3 Minimum Perfect Square Sum of Entries

Example 3.5. A *block-wise magic square* of order 18 for consecutive fraction numbers entries $\{15/2, 17/2, \dots, 659/2, 661/2\}$ is given by

mgc	18x18					https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	https://numbers-magic.com/	@IJTANEJA	©IJT	3042									
7.5	313.5	312.5	295.5	24.5	60.5	8.5	314.5	311.5	296.5	23.5	59.5	9.5	315.5	310.5	297.5	22.5	58.5	3042	
276.5	78.5	258.5	79.5	97.5	223.5	275.5	77.5	257.5	80.5	98.5	224.5	274.5	76.5	256.5	81.5	99.5	225.5	3042	
222.5	205.5	133.5	150.5	186.5	115.5	221.5	206.5	134.5	149.5	185.5	116.5	220.5	207.5	135.5	148.5	184.5	117.5	3042	
168.5	132.5	187.5	204.5	151.5	169.5	167.5	131.5	188.5	203.5	152.5	170.5	166.5	130.5	189.5	202.5	153.5	171.5	3042	
61.5	240.5	96.5	241.5	259.5	114.5	62.5	239.5	95.5	242.5	260.5	113.5	63.5	238.5	94.5	243.5	261.5	112.5	3042	
277.5	43.5	25.5	42.5	294.5	330.5	278.5	44.5	26.5	41.5	293.5	329.5	279.5	45.5	27.5	40.5	292.5	328.5	3042	
10.5	316.5	309.5	298.5	21.5	57.5	11.5	317.5	308.5	299.5	20.5	56.5	12.5	318.5	307.5	300.5	19.5	55.5	3042	
273.5	75.5	255.5	82.5	100.5	226.5	272.5	74.5	254.5	83.5	101.5	227.5	271.5	73.5	253.5	84.5	102.5	228.5	3042	
219.5	208.5	136.5	147.5	183.5	118.5	218.5	209.5	137.5	146.5	182.5	119.5	217.5	210.5	138.5	145.5	181.5	120.5	3042	
165.5	129.5	190.5	201.5	154.5	172.5	164.5	128.5	191.5	200.5	155.5	173.5	163.5	127.5	192.5	199.5	156.5	174.5	3042	
64.5	237.5	93.5	244.5	262.5	111.5	65.5	236.5	92.5	245.5	263.5	110.5	66.5	235.5	91.5	246.5	264.5	109.5	3042	
280.5	46.5	28.5	39.5	291.5	327.5	281.5	47.5	29.5	38.5	290.5	326.5	282.5	48.5	30.5	37.5	289.5	325.5	3042	
13.5	319.5	306.5	301.5	18.5	54.5	14.5	320.5	305.5	302.5	17.5	53.5	15.5	321.5	304.5	303.5	16.5	52.5	3042	
270.5	72.5	252.5	85.5	103.5	229.5	269.5	71.5	251.5	86.5	104.5	230.5	268.5	70.5	250.5	87.5	105.5	231.5	3042	
216.5	211.5	139.5	144.5	180.5	121.5	215.5	212.5	140.5	143.5	179.5	122.5	214.5	213.5	141.5	142.5	178.5	123.5	3042	
162.5	126.5	193.5	198.5	157.5	175.5	161.5	125.5	194.5	197.5	158.5	176.5	160.5	124.5	195.5	196.5	159.5	177.5	3042	
67.5	234.5	90.5	247.5	265.5	108.5	68.5	233.5	89.5	248.5	266.5	107.5	69.5	232.5	88.5	249.5	267.5	106.5	3042	
283.5	49.5	31.5	36.5	288.5	324.5	284.5	50.5	32.5	35.5	287.5	323.5	285.5	51.5	33.5	34.5	286.5	322.5	3042	
3042	3042	3042	3042	3042	3042	3042	3042	3042	3042	3042	3042	3042	3042	3042	3042	3042	3042	3042	3042

The **block-wise** magic square of order 18 given in Example 3.5 is with **minimum perfect square** sum of entries. The entries sum is **minimum perfect square**. The blocks of order 6 are magic squares with equal magic sums. See below the details

$$S_{18 \times 18} = 3042; \quad T_{324} := 54756 = 234^2;$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} = 1014; \quad T_{36} := 6084 = 78^2.$$

For more details refer author’s work [14, 15, 16, 17, 18].

3.2 Latin Square Distributions

Let’s consider the Latin square distributions of magic square of order 18 given in Examples 2.1 and 2.2.

Example 3.6. *Let’s consider a pair of Latin square decomposition as given below:*

mgc	18x18	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	https://numbers-magic.com/	@IJTANEJA	©IJT	171												
2	3	1	11	10	12	14	15	13	17	16	18	8	9	7	5	4	6	171
1	2	3	12	11	10	13	14	15	18	17	16	7	8	9	6	5	4	171
3	1	2	10	12	11	15	13	14	16	18	17	9	7	8	4	6	5	171
14	15	13	5	4	6	17	16	18	8	9	7	11	10	12	2	3	1	171
13	14	15	6	5	4	18	17	16	7	8	9	12	11	10	1	2	3	171
15	13	14	4	6	5	16	18	17	9	7	8	10	12	11	3	1	2	171
5	4	6	2	3	1	8	9	7	14	15	13	17	16	18	11	10	12	171
6	5	4	1	2	3	7	8	9	13	14	15	18	17	16	12	11	10	171
4	6	5	3	1	2	9	7	8	15	13	14	16	18	17	10	12	11	171
17	16	18	8	9	7	2	3	1	11	10	12	5	4	6	14	15	13	171
18	17	16	7	8	9	1	2	3	12	11	10	6	5	4	13	14	15	171
16	18	17	9	7	8	3	1	2	10	12	11	4	6	5	15	13	14	171
11	10	12	17	16	18	5	4	6	2	3	1	14	15	13	8	9	7	171
12	11	10	18	17	16	6	5	4	1	2	3	13	14	15	7	8	9	171
10	12	11	16	18	17	4	6	5	3	1	2	15	13	14	9	7	8	171
8	9	7	14	15	13	11	10	12	5	4	6	2	3	1	17	16	18	171
7	8	9	13	14	15	12	11	10	6	5	4	1	2	3	18	17	16	171
9	7	8	15	13	14	10	12	11	4	6	5	3	1	2	16	18	17	171
171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171

and

mgc	18x18	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	https://numbers-magic.com/	@IJTANEJA	©IJT	171												
1	3	2	13	15	14	12	10	11	12	10	11	13	15	14	6	4	5	171
3	2	1	15	14	13	10	11	12	10	11	12	15	14	13	4	5	6	171
2	1	3	14	13	15	11	12	10	11	12	10	14	13	15	5	6	4	171
13	15	14	1	3	2	13	15	14	6	4	5	7	9	8	13	15	14	171
15	14	13	3	2	1	15	14	13	4	5	6	9	8	7	15	14	13	171
14	13	15	2	1	3	14	13	15	5	6	4	8	7	9	14	13	15	171
18	16	17	18	16	17	1	3	2	7	9	8	1	3	2	12	10	11	171
16	17	18	16	17	18	3	2	1	9	8	7	3	2	1	10	11	12	171
17	18	16	17	18	16	2	1	3	8	7	9	2	1	3	11	12	10	171
6	4	5	12	10	11	12	10	11	18	16	17	12	10	11	1	3	2	171
4	5	6	10	11	12	10	11	12	16	17	18	10	11	12	3	2	1	171
5	6	4	11	12	10	11	12	10	17	18	16	11	12	10	2	1	3	171
1	3	2	7	9	8	13	15	14	7	9	8	18	16	17	7	9	8	171
3	2	1	9	8	7	15	14	13	9	8	7	16	17	18	9	8	7	171
2	1	3	8	7	9	14	13	15	8	7	9	17	18	16	8	7	9	171
18	16	17	6	4	5	6	4	5	7	9	8	6	4	5	18	16	17	171
16	17	18	4	5	6	4	5	6	9	8	7	4	5	6	16	17	18	171
17	18	16	5	6	4	5	6	4	8	7	9	5	6	4	17	18	16	171
171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171

By application of the formula $18 \times (A - 1) + B$, we get the magic square given in Example 3.25.

Example 3.7. Let's consider a pair of Latin square decomposition as given below:

mgc	18x18	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	https://numbers-magic.com/	@IJTANEJA	©IJT	171												
1	18	17	17	1	3	1	18	17	17	1	3	1	18	17	17	1	3	171
15	4	14	5	6	13	15	4	14	5	6	13	15	4	14	5	6	13	171
12	12	8	8	10	7	12	12	8	8	10	7	12	12	8	8	10	7	171
9	7	11	11	9	10	9	7	11	11	9	10	9	7	11	11	9	10	171
4	13	5	14	15	6	4	13	5	14	15	6	4	13	5	14	15	6	171
16	3	2	2	16	18	16	3	2	2	16	18	16	3	2	2	16	18	171
1	18	17	17	1	3	1	18	17	17	1	3	1	18	17	17	1	3	171
15	4	14	5	6	13	15	4	14	5	6	13	15	4	14	5	6	13	171
12	12	8	8	10	7	12	12	8	8	10	7	12	12	8	8	10	7	171
9	7	11	11	9	10	9	7	11	11	9	10	9	7	11	11	9	10	171
4	13	5	14	15	6	4	13	5	14	15	6	4	13	5	14	15	6	171
16	3	2	2	16	18	16	3	2	2	16	18	16	3	2	2	16	18	171
1	18	17	17	1	3	1	18	17	17	1	3	1	18	17	17	1	3	171
15	4	14	5	6	13	15	4	14	5	6	13	15	4	14	5	6	13	171
12	12	8	8	10	7	12	12	8	8	10	7	12	12	8	8	10	7	171
9	7	11	11	9	10	9	7	11	11	9	10	9	7	11	11	9	10	171
4	13	5	14	15	6	4	13	5	14	15	6	4	13	5	14	15	6	171
16	3	2	2	16	18	16	3	2	2	16	18	16	3	2	2	16	18	171
171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171

and

mgc	18x18	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	https://numbers-magic.com/	@JTANEJA	©IJT	171
1	1 18 1 18 18	2 2 17 2 17 17	3 3 16 3 16 16	171		
18	18 18 1 1 1	17 17 17 2 2 2	16 16 16 3 3 3	171		
18	1 1 18 18 1	17 2 2 17 17 2	16 3 3 16 16 3	171		
18	18 1 18 1 1	17 17 2 17 2 2	16 16 3 16 3 3	171		
1	18 18 1 1 18	2 17 17 2 2 17	3 16 16 3 3 16	171		
1	1 1 1 18 18 18	2 2 2 17 17 17	3 3 3 16 16 16	171		
4	4 4 15 4 15 15	5 5 14 5 14 14	6 6 13 6 13 13	171		
15	15 15 15 4 4 4	14 14 14 5 5 5	13 13 13 6 6 6	171		
15	4 4 15 15 4	14 5 5 14 14 5	13 6 6 13 13 6	171		
15	15 15 4 15 4 4	14 14 5 14 5 5	13 13 6 13 6 6	171		
4	15 15 4 4 15	5 14 14 5 5 14	6 13 13 6 6 13	171		
4	4 4 4 15 15 15	5 5 5 14 14 14	6 6 6 13 13 13	171		
7	7 7 12 7 12 12	8 8 11 8 11 11	9 9 10 9 10 10	171		
12	12 12 12 7 7 7	11 11 11 8 8 8	10 10 10 9 9 9	171		
12	7 7 12 12 7	11 8 8 11 11 8	10 9 9 10 10 9	171		
12	12 12 7 12 7 7	11 11 8 11 8 8	10 10 9 10 9 9	171		
7	12 12 7 7 12	8 11 11 8 8 11	9 10 10 9 9 10	171		
7	7 7 7 12 12 12	8 8 8 11 11 11	9 9 9 10 10 10	171		
171	171 171 171 171 171 171	171 171 171 171 171 171	171 171 171 171 171 171	171		

By application of the formula $18 \times (A - 1) + B$, we get the magic square given in Example 3.26.

We observe from above two examples that the Latin square distribution is not orthogonally diagonalized. Below is a third example, where the distribution is "SOLDS". See below

Example 3.8. Let's consider a pair of Latin square decomposition as given below:

mgc	18x18	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	https://numbers-magic.com/	@IJTANEJA	©IJT	171													
1	8	9	11	10	4	14	5	15	3	16	18	17	13	6	7	2	12	171	
17	2	8	9	11	10	5	6	14	4	15	16	12	7	18	3	1	13	171	
15	16	3	8	9	11	10	7	13	5	14	1	18	17	4	2	12	6	171	
2	14	15	4	8	9	11	18	12	6	13	17	16	5	3	1	7	10	171	
16	3	13	14	5	8	9	17	1	7	12	15	6	4	2	18	10	11	171	
14	15	4	12	13	6	8	16	2	18	1	7	5	3	17	10	11	9	171	
18	13	14	5	1	12	7	15	3	17	2	6	4	16	10	11	9	8	171	
3	4	5	6	7	18	17	8	11	9	10	2	1	12	13	14	15	16	171	
12	1	2	3	4	5	6	10	9	11	8	13	14	15	16	17	18	7	171	
4	5	6	7	18	17	16	11	8	10	9	3	2	1	12	13	14	15	171	
5	6	7	18	17	16	15	9	10	8	11	4	3	2	1	12	13	14	171	
8	9	11	10	3	15	13	4	16	2	17	12	7	18	14	5	6	1	171	
9	11	10	2	16	14	12	3	17	1	18	8	13	6	7	15	4	5	171	
11	10	1	17	15	13	4	2	18	12	7	9	8	14	5	6	16	3	171	
10	12	18	16	14	3	2	1	7	13	6	11	9	8	15	4	5	17	171	
13	7	17	15	2	1	18	12	6	14	5	10	11	9	8	16	3	4	171	
6	18	16	1	12	7	3	13	5	15	4	14	10	11	9	8	17	2	171	
7	17	12	13	6	2	1	14	4	16	3	5	15	10	11	9	8	18	171	
171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171

and

mgc	18x18	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	https://numbers-magic.com/	@JTANEJA	©IJT	171												
1	17	15	2	16	14	18	3	12	4	5	8	9	11	10	13	6	7	171
8	2	16	14	3	15	13	4	1	5	6	9	11	10	12	7	18	17	171
9	8	3	15	13	4	14	5	2	6	7	11	10	1	18	17	16	12	171
11	9	8	4	14	12	5	6	3	7	18	10	2	17	16	15	1	13	171
10	11	9	8	5	13	1	7	4	18	17	3	16	15	14	2	12	6	171
4	10	11	9	8	6	12	18	5	17	16	15	14	13	3	1	7	2	171
14	5	10	11	9	8	7	17	6	16	15	13	12	4	2	18	3	1	171
5	6	7	18	17	16	15	8	10	11	9	4	3	2	1	12	13	14	171
15	14	13	12	1	2	3	11	9	8	10	16	17	18	7	6	5	4	171
3	4	5	6	7	18	17	9	11	10	8	2	1	12	13	14	15	16	171
16	15	14	13	12	1	2	10	8	9	11	17	18	7	6	5	4	3	171
18	16	1	17	15	7	6	2	13	3	4	12	8	9	11	10	14	5	171
17	12	18	16	6	5	4	1	14	2	3	7	13	8	9	11	10	15	171
13	7	17	5	4	3	16	12	15	1	2	18	6	14	8	9	11	10	171
6	18	4	3	2	17	10	13	16	12	1	14	7	5	15	8	9	11	171
7	3	2	1	18	10	11	14	17	13	12	5	15	6	4	16	8	9	171
2	1	12	7	10	11	9	15	18	14	13	6	4	16	5	3	17	8	171
12	13	6	10	11	9	8	16	7	15	14	1	5	3	17	4	2	18	171
171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171

By application of the formula $18 \times (A - 1) + B$, we get the following magic square of order 18:

mgc	18x18 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA ©IJT																	2925
1	143	159	182	178	68	252	75	264	40	275	314	297	227	100	121	24	205	2925
296	20	142	158	183	177	85	94	235	59	258	279	209	118	318	43	18	233	2925
261	278	39	141	157	184	176	113	218	78	241	11	316	289	72	35	214	102	2925
29	243	260	58	140	156	185	312	201	97	234	298	272	89	52	15	109	175	2925
280	47	225	242	77	139	145	295	4	126	215	255	106	69	32	308	174	186	2925
238	262	65	207	224	96	138	288	23	323	16	123	86	49	291	163	187	146	2925
320	221	244	83	9	206	115	269	42	304	33	103	66	274	164	198	147	127	2925
41	60	79	108	125	322	303	134	190	155	171	22	3	200	217	246	265	284	2925
213	14	31	48	55	74	93	173	153	188	136	232	251	270	277	294	311	112	2925
57	76	95	114	313	306	287	189	137	172	152	38	19	12	211	230	249	268	2925
88	105	122	319	300	271	254	154	170	135	191	71	54	25	6	203	220	237	2925
144	160	181	179	51	259	222	56	283	21	292	210	116	315	245	82	104	5	2925
161	192	180	34	276	239	202	37	302	2	309	133	229	98	117	263	64	87	2925
193	169	17	293	256	219	70	30	321	199	110	162	132	248	80	99	281	46	2925
168	216	310	273	236	53	28	13	124	228	91	194	151	131	267	62	81	299	2925
223	111	290	253	36	10	317	212	107	247	84	167	195	150	130	286	44	63	2925
92	307	282	7	208	119	45	231	90	266	67	240	166	196	149	129	305	26	2925
120	301	204	226	101	27	8	250	61	285	50	73	257	165	197	148	128	324	2925
2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925	2925

The magic square given in Example 3.27 shall be used in a topic on **upside-down, mirror looking and water reflection** magic squares.

For more details refer author’s work [49]. The next subsection is based on the Latin square distributions.

3.3 Upside-Down, Mirror Looking and Water Reflection

Let's consider the following image:

Source: <https://www.mathsisfun.com/definitions/vertical-flip.html>

From the above image we understand that **horizontal flip** is same as **mirror looking image** and the **vertical flip** is same as **water reflection image**. The same terms are given in **paint brush of microsoft**. Let's see how it works on numbers.

Let's consider following 9 digits written in digital form:

0-1-2-3-4-5-6-7-8-9

- **180° Rotation**

6-8-1-9-5-4-6-2-1-0

In this case, the readable numbers are 0, 1, 2, 5, 6, 8 and 9 where the number 6 becomes 9 and 9 as 6. Thus the **survival numbers** after 180° rotation are 0, 1, 2, 5, 6, 8 and 9. Sometimes we call them as **upside-down** numbers.

- **Mirror Looking**

It is same as **horizontal flip** as describe above. In this case, we have

2-8-1-2-2-4-6-5-1-0

In this case, the readable numbers are 0, 1, 2, 5 and 8, where 2 becomes 5 and 5 as 2. Thus the **survival numbers** after **horizontal flip** are 0, 1, 2, 5 and 8. Sometimes we call them as **mirror-looking** numbers.

- **Water Reflection**

It is same as **vertical flip** as describe above. In this case, we have

0-1-5-3-4-2-2-1-8-2

In this case, the readable numbers are 0, 1, 2, 3, 5 and 8, where 2 becomes 5 and 5 as 2. Thus the **survival numbers** after **vertical flip** are 0, 1, 2, 3, 5 and 8. For the first time we call these numbers as **water reflection** or **water reflexive** numbers.

We observe that the numbers 0, 1, 2, 5 and 8 are in all the three situations, i.e., these are **upside-down**, **mirror-looking** and **water reflexive**. We call them as **universal numbers** provided they are written in **digital form**. There left only one number 3. It is only **water reflexive**. While the numbers 6 and 9 are only **upside-down**.

There is a lot of work by author on **upside-down** and **mirror-looking** numbers. This work is concentrated only towards magic squares having **water reflexive** numbers, i.e., 0, 1, 2, 3, 5 and 8. The numbers 0, 1, 2, 5 and 8 are already studied previously. This work brings magic squares of order 14 to 16 specially in number 3 along with 0, 1, 2, 5 and 8.

3.4 Upside-Down and Mirror-Looking

This subsection brings magic squares of orders 18 written in such way that we can make 180° rotation and/or see in the mirror, and are able to read the entries again resulting in new magic squares. It is possible due to the fact that the digits 0, 1, 2, 5, 6, 8 and 9 are readable when we make them 180° rotation or see in the mirror.

Example 3.9. *The magic squares of order 18 for the digits (0, 1, 2, 5, 8) is given by*

0101	5222	5525	1088	5818	2581	2255	1121	8285	1552	1210	8512	5158	2882	8815	1828	2151	8111
2252	1010	8822	5225	1185	5521	2558	1201	8182	1888	1511	5155	2881	8518	2128	0151	5812	8215
2555	2288	1111	8522	8825	1282	5201	1510	5881	2185	1812	2858	8221	0128	1051	5515	8118	5152
8810	2552	2285	1212	8222	8525	1581	1811	5558	0182	2115	8101	1028	1151	5218	5821	5188	2855
1858	8511	2588	2282	1515	8122	8225	2112	5255	1081	0118	1128	1251	8821	5501	5185	2852	5810
8125	2155	8212	2585	2281	1818	5822	0115	8852	1158	1021	1551	8501	5210	5182	2888	5511	1228
5522	5825	0152	8115	2582	2258	2121	1018	8588	1255	1101	8210	8811	5181	2885	5212	1528	1851
0211	0112	1015	1118	1221	1501	1810	2222	5128	2551	2825	5585	5888	8152	8255	8558	8881	5282
8582	8281	8158	5855	5552	5288	8885	2851	2525	5122	2228	1011	0110	2101	1821	1518	1215	1112
5215	8818	8521	8201	8110	5811	5512	5125	2251	2828	2522	2181	1882	1585	1288	1152	1055	0158
1012	1115	1218	1521	1801	2110	0111	2528	2822	2225	5151	8882	5285	5588	5852	8155	8258	8581
1285	5551	5828	0181	2811	5115	1082	8555	1110	8121	8288	5252	2218	2512	1558	8801	1825	2122
5851	8128	2182	2810	5112	0185	1188	8858	1001	8218	8552	1822	5555	2215	2511	1281	5221	1525
8228	1885	2801	5111	2188	1052	8151	5281	0121	8515	8855	1225	1522	5858	2212	2510	1182	5518
1588	2821	5110	1852	0155	8251	8528	5582	2118	8812	5258	5815	1125	1222	8181	2211	2501	1085
2818	5101	1555	2158	8551	8828	1252	5885	1815	5211	5581	0188	8112	1025	1122	8282	2210	2521
5121	1258	1881	8851	5228	1155	2815	8188	1512	5510	5882	2518	2152	8211	0125	1022	8585	2201
1181	1582	5251	5528	1058	2812	5118	8252	1211	5801	8185	2221	2515	1855	8510	2125	0122	8888

0808	5528	5851	1188	8022	5181	2858	1225	8285	2155	1811	8518	5280	5282	8821	2252	2552	8112
2855	1111	8828	5551	1285	5825	5180	1808	8182	2288	2112	5258	5281	8522	2552	0852	8018	8221
5158	2888	1212	8528	8851	1882	5508	2111	8081	2585	2218	5280	8225	0852	1152	5821	8122	5255
8811	5155	2885	1818	8228	8551	2181	2212	5880	0882	2521	8108	1152	1252	5522	8025	5288	5258
2280	8512	5188	2882	2121	8128	8251	2518	5558	1181	0822	1252	1852	8825	5808	5285	5255	8011
8151	2558	8218	5185	2881	2222	8028	0821	8855	1280	1125	2152	8508	5511	5282	5288	5812	1852
5828	8051	0855	8121	5182	2880	2525	1122	8588	1858	1208	8211	8812	5281	5285	5518	2152	2252
2512	0818	1121	1222	1825	2108	2211	2828	5252	5152	5251	5885	8088	8155	8258	8580	8881	5582
8582	8281	8180	8058	5855	5588	8885	5252	5151	5228	2852	1112	0811	2508	2225	2122	1821	1218
5521	8822	8525	8208	8111	8012	5818	5251	2852	5252	5128	2581	2282	2185	1888	1255	1158	0880
1118	1221	1822	2125	2208	2511	0812	5152	5228	2851	5252	8882	5585	5888	8055	8158	8280	8581
1885	5852	8052	0881	5212	5221	1182	8558	1211	8125	8288	5555	2822	5118	2180	8808	2251	2528
8052	8152	2582	5211	5218	0885	1288	8880	1108	8222	8555	2228	5858	2821	5112	1881	5525	2151
8252	2285	5208	5212	2588	1155	8152	5581	0825	8521	8858	1851	2128	8080	2818	5111	1282	5822
2188	5225	5211	2255	0858	8252	8552	5882	2522	8818	5580	8021	1251	1828	8181	2812	5108	1185
5222	5208	2158	2580	8552	8852	1855	8085	2221	5512	5881	0888	8118	1151	1228	8282	2811	5125
5225	1880	2281	8852	5552	1258	5221	8188	2118	5811	8082	5122	2555	8212	0851	1128	8585	2808
1281	2182	5552	5852	1180	5218	5222	8255	1812	8008	8185	2825	5121	2258	8511	2551	0828	8888

It is *upside-down and mirror-looking*, i.e., *universal magic square* with magic sum $S_{18 \times 18}(0, 1, 2, 5, 8) := 72215$.

Example 3.10. The magic squares of order 18 for the digits (2, 5, 6, 8, 9) is given by

6969	5222	5525	9688	5898	2589	2255	9929	8285	9552	9296	8592	5958	2882	8895	9828	2959	8999
2252	9696	8822	5225	9985	5529	2558	9269	8982	9888	9599	5955	2889	8598	2928	6959	5892	8295
2555	2288	9999	8522	8825	9282	5269	9596	5889	2985	9892	2858	8229	6928	9659	5595	8998	5952
8896	2552	2285	9292	8222	8525	9589	9899	5558	6982	2995	8969	9628	9959	5298	5829	5988	2855
9858	8599	2588	2282	9595	8922	8225	2992	5255	9689	6998	9928	9259	8829	5569	5985	2852	5896
8925	2955	8292	2585	2289	9898	5822	6995	8852	9958	9629	9559	8569	5296	5982	2888	5599	9228
5522	5825	6952	8995	2582	2258	2929	9698	8588	9255	9969	8296	8899	5989	2885	5292	9528	9859
2999	6992	9695	9998	9229	9569	9896	2222	5928	2559	2825	5585	5888	8952	8255	8558	8889	5282
8582	8289	8958	5855	5552	5288	8885	2859	2525	5922	2228	9699	6996	2969	9829	9598	9295	9992
5295	8898	8529	8269	8996	5899	5592	5925	2259	2828	2522	2989	9882	9585	9288	9952	9655	6958
9692	9995	9298	9529	9869	2996	6999	2528	2822	2225	5959	8882	5285	5588	5852	8955	8258	8589
9285	5559	5828	6989	2899	5995	9682	8555	9996	8929	8288	5252	2298	2592	9558	8869	9825	2922
5859	8928	2982	2896	5992	6985	9988	8858	9669	8298	8552	9822	5555	2295	2599	9289	5229	9525
8228	9885	2869	5999	2988	9652	8959	5289	6929	8595	8855	9225	9522	5858	2292	2596	9982	5598
9588	2829	5996	9852	6955	8259	8528	5582	2998	8892	5258	5895	9925	9222	8989	2299	2569	9685
2898	5969	9555	2958	8559	8828	9252	5885	9895	5299	5589	6988	8992	9625	9922	8282	2296	2529
5929	9258	9889	8859	5228	9955	2895	8988	9592	5596	5882	2598	2952	8299	6925	9622	8585	2269
9989	9582	5259	5528	9658	2892	5998	8252	9299	5869	8985	2229	2595	9855	8596	2925	6922	8888

It is *upside-down* magic square with magic sum $S_{18 \times 18}(2, 5, 6, 8, 9) := 123321$.

Example 3.11. The magic squares of order 18 for the digits $(0, 1, 6, 8, 9)$ is given by

0101	9666	9969	1088	9818	6981	6699	1161	8689	1996	1610	8916	9198	6886	8819	1868	6191	8111
6696	1010	8866	9669	1189	9961	6998	1601	8186	1888	1911	9199	6881	8918	6168	0191	9816	8619
6999	6688	1111	8966	8869	1686	9601	1910	9881	6189	1816	6898	8661	0168	1091	9919	8118	9196
8810	6996	6689	1616	8666	8969	1981	1811	9998	186	6119	8101	1068	1191	9618	9861	9188	6899
1898	8911	6988	6686	1919	8166	8669	6116	9699	1081	0118	1168	1691	8861	9901	9189	6896	9810
8169	6199	8616	6989	6681	1818	9866	0119	8896	1198	1061	1991	8901	9610	9186	6888	9911	1668
9966	9869	0196	8119	6986	6698	6161	1018	8988	1699	1101	8610	8811	9181	6889	9616	1968	1891
6111	0116	1019	1118	1661	1901	1810	6666	9168	6991	6869	9989	9888	8196	8699	8998	8881	9686
8986	8681	8198	9899	9996	9688	8889	6891	6969	9166	6668	1011	0110	6101	1861	1918	1619	1116
9619	8818	8961	8601	8110	9811	9916	9169	6691	6868	6966	6181	1886	1989	1688	1196	1099	0198
1016	1119	1618	1961	1801	6110	0111	6968	6866	6669	9191	8886	9689	9988	9896	8199	8698	8981
1689	9991	9868	0181	6811	9119	1086	8999	1110	8161	8688	9696	6618	6916	1998	8801	1869	6166
9891	8168	6186	6810	9116	0189	1188	8898	1001	8618	8996	1866	9999	6619	6911	1681	9661	1969
8668	1889	6801	9111	6188	1096	8191	9681	0161	8919	8899	1669	1966	9898	6616	6910	1186	9918
1988	6861	9110	1896	0199	8691	8968	9986	6118	8816	9698	9819	1169	1666	8181	6611	6901	1089
6818	9101	1999	6198	8991	8868	1696	9889	1819	9611	9981	0188	8116	1069	1166	8686	6610	6961
9161	1698	1881	8891	9668	1199	6819	8188	1916	9910	9886	6918	6196	8611	0169	1066	8989	6601
1181	1986	9691	9968	1098	6816	9118	8696	1611	9801	8189	6661	6919	1899	8910	6169	0166	8888

It is *upside-down* magic square with magic sum $S_{18 \times 18}(0, 1, 6, 8, 9) := 107767$.

Example 3.12. The magic squares of order 18 for the digits (1, 8) is given by

181111181	818888811	818888811	818881888	181111188	181188818	111111111	888888818	888881888	888881881	111111881	111188888	111818111	8881881881	888188181	8881818818	111818118	111818188
8188188818	181181188	818818811	181181888	181188881	818811181	881888888	118811881	881881888	118818811	118818818	881181111	8881181888	118818118	888118181	1188818818	118881881	888118111
8118188818	811818881	188181888	188188811	811811188	188181181	811888888	811888818	188118811	188181888	811881881	188111111	8811181888	8811181881	1188818818	118888181	881118118	118881811
1881888818	188181188	811811888	811818811	188188881	811811181	188188888	188111881	811881881	811888188	188188118	811881111	1188881888	1188818118	881118818	881118181	1188881881	881118111
181181181	818811188	181188811	818811888	818818881	1811888818	118811111	881181881	118818188	881181881	881888118	118818888	118818111	888118118	11888181	888118818	888181881	118881888
818881181	181188811	181111888	181188111	818881188	818888818	888881111	111188118	111118811	111181888	888881881	888888888	888181811	1118181881	111818818	111818181	888181818	888188188
111811111	888188818	888188188	888181881	111811881	111818888	181118111	8188881881	818888181	8188818818	181118118	181181888	111111181	888888881	888888111	888881888	111111188	111188818
888188888	118818881	888181888	118818811	118888188	888111111	8188181888	181181818	818818181	181181888	181881881	818818111	881888818	118811188	881888111	118811888	118818881	881811818
881188888	881188118	118881881	118888188	881111881	118881111	8118181888	8118181881	1881818818	188188181	811818118	188181811	811888818	811888881	188111888	188188111	811881188	188111181
118888888	118881881	881118811	881181888	118888818	881111111	1881881888	188181818	811818818	811818181	1881881881	811818111	188188818	188111188	811881888	811888811	188188811	811881181
111881111	888111881	111888188	888118811	888188188	111888888	181181811	818818118	181881818	818818818	818818881	181881888	118811181	881181188	118818811	881181888	881888811	1188188818
888181111	111818818	111818811	111818188	888181881	888188888	818881811	181181881	181118818	181181818	818881818	818888188	888881181	111188811	11111888	111188111	888881188	888888818
111118111	8888881881	888888181	8888818818	111118118	111181888	111811181	888188881	888188811	888181888	111811188	1118188818	181111111	818888818	818888188	818881881	181111881	181188888
8811881888	118818118	881888181	118818818	1188181881	881818111	888188818	118881188	888188111	118818888	118888811	888111181	818818888	181181881	818818188	181188818	181888118	818811111
8118881888	8118881881	188118818	188181818	811881818	188118111	881188818	881188811	118881888	118888811	881111188	118881181	811818888	811818818	188188811	188188188	81181881	188181111
188181888	188118118	8118818818	811888181	188181881	811881811	118888818	118881188	881111888	881188111	118888811	881111181	188188888	188181881	811818811	811818188	188188818	811811111
118818111	881181818	118818181	8811818818	8811881881	1188181888	118881181	888111188	118888811	888111888	888188811	118888818	181181111	818811881	181881888	818818811	818818818	181888888
888881811	111181881	111118818	111181818	888881818	888888188	888181181	111818881	111811888	111818811	888181188	888188818	818881111	181188118	181118811	181181888	818881881	818888888

In each case all the blocks of order 6 are magic squares with equal magic sums. The magic sums are given by

$$S_{18 \times 18}(1, 8) := 89999999991; \quad S_{6 \times 6}(1, 8) := 29999999997$$

It is upside-down and mirror-looking, i.e., universal magic square.

Example 3.13. The magic squares of order 18 for the digits (1, 8), (2, 5) and (6, 9) are given by

252222252	525555522	525555222	525552255	252222255	252225525	222222222	555555225	555552255	555552552	222222552	222225555	222525222	555255252	555255252	222525225	222525255
525525552	252252255	525525522	252252255	252255522	525522252	552255555	225522252	552255225	225522552	225522255	552252222	555225255	222525225	555225252	222525225	555225222
522525552	522525522	255252255	255255222	522522255	255252252	522555555	522555225	255222552	255225255	522522552	255222222	552225255	552225252	225525252	225525225	225525222
255255552	255252255	522522255	522525222	255255522	522522252	255225555	255222252	522555225	522555225	255225225	522552222	225552255	225525225	552225252	552225225	225525222
252252252	525522255	252255222	525522255	525525522	252255525	225522222	552252252	225522255	552252552	552255225	225525555	222525222	555222252	222525225	555222252	555225255
525522252	252225522	252222255	252225222	525522255	525555525	555522222	222225225	222222552	222225255	555522552	555555555	555252522	222525252	222522255	222522252	555252555
222522222	555255225	555252255	555252552	222522252	222525555	252222222	525552552	525552252	525552552	252222255	252222555	222222252	555555522	555555222	555522555	222222255
555225555	222522252	555225225	222525522	222555225	555222222	525525255	252225225	525525225	252225225	252225252	525522222	552225255	222522255	552225222	225522255	225525222
552225555	552225225	225525252	225552255	552222252	225552222	522525255	522525252	255225252	255225225	522522225	255225222	522555525	522555522	255222255	255225222	522522225
225555555	225522252	552222252	552225225	225555225	552222222	255255255	255225225	522522252	255225225	255225252	522522222	255225255	255222255	522555222	255225222	522522225
222522222	555222252	222552255	555222522	555225225	222555555	252225222	525522225	252225225	525522552	525522552	252225255	225522252	552225225	225525222	552225255	225525225
555222222	222525225	222522252	222522255	555222252	555225225	525522222	252225252	252222255	252225225	525522225	525552255	555522252	222225222	222222255	222225222	555522255
222222222	555552252	555552252	555552525	222222225	222225255	222222222	555225222	555225222	555222255	222222255	222225255	252222222	525555225	525552255	252222252	252225255
552225255	225522225	552225222	225522252	225522252	552225222	555225225	222522255	555225222	222522255	222522255	555222222	525225255	252225222	525522255	252225222	252225222
522552555	522552552	255222255	255225222	522522255	255222222	552225225	552225222	225522255	225555222	552222255	225522252	522525555	522525225	255225222	255222255	255222222
255222255	255222225	522525225	522555222	255222252	522522222	225555525	225522255	552222255	552225222	225555522	552222252	255225555	255222252	522522252	522522255	255222222
225522222	552225225	225525222	552225225	552225252	225525255	222522222	555222255	222555222	555222255	555225222	222555525	252222222	525522252	252225225	525522252	252225255
555522222	222225252	222222255	222225222	555522252	555552255	555222222	222225222	222222255	222225222	555222255	555225222	252225225	252222252	252222255	252225222	525555555

In each case all the blocks of order 6 are magic squares with equal magic sums. The magic sums are given by

$$S_{18 \times 18}(2, 5) := 69999999993; \quad S_{6 \times 6}(2, 5) := 2333333331$$

It is only *upside-down* magic square.

Example 3.14. The magic squares of order 18 for the digits (1, 8), (2, 5) and (6, 9) are given by

696666696	969999966	969999666	969996699	696666699	696669969	666666666	999999669	999996699	999996966	666666996	666699999	666966966	999699696	999696696	999696969	666966969	666969666
969969969	696696699	969969666	696696999	696699966	969966696	996699999	669966996	996996699	669966966	669969969	996696666	999696999	666996669	999696696	666996969	666999696	999666966
966969969	966969966	699696699	699699666	966966699	699696696	966999999	966999669	699666996	699666969	966996996	699666666	996696999	996696966	669996969	669996696	996666969	669996666
699699969	699696699	966966699	966996666	699699966	966966696	699669999	699666996	966996996	966999669	699669669	966996666	669999699	669996669	996666969	996669696	669996996	996666966
696696696	969966699	696699966	969966699	969969966	696699969	669966666	996696696	669969669	996696996	996699669	669969999	666996966	999666969	666996696	999666969	999669696	666996999
969996669	696669966	696666699	696669666	969996699	969999669	999996666	666699669	666669966	666669669	999996996	999999999	999696966	666969696	666966969	666966966	999696699	999696999
666966666	999699669	999696699	999696996	666966696	666969999	696666966	969996996	969996696	969996969	696666969	696666999	666666696	999999966	999999666	999966999	666666699	666669969
999669999	666996696	999669669	666996996	666999669	999666666	969969699	696696699	969966696	696696969	696699696	969966966	996699969	669966699	996699666	669966999	669969966	996696696
996669999	996669969	669996996	669996699	996666996	669996666	966969699	966969696	699696996	699696696	966966969	699696666	966999969	966999666	699666999	699669666	966996699	699666696
669999999	669996696	996666996	996669669	669999669	996666666	699699699	699696669	966969969	966966966	699699696	966966966	699699969	699666699	966996699	966999666	699699666	966996696
666996666	999666996	666999669	999666996	999669966	666999999	696696966	969966969	696696696	969966969	969969966	696699699	669966696	996696699	669969666	996699966	996699966	669969969
999696666	666969969	666966996	666969669	999696699	999699999	969996966	696669666	696669969	969996999	969996669	999996666	666669966	666669999	666669666	666669966	999996699	999999669
996699699	669969669	996699666	669966996	669969966	996696966	999669969	666996699	999669666	666996699	666999966	999666696	969969999	696696696	969966699	696696966	696699669	969966666
966996999	966996996	699666996	699669666	966996969	699666966	996669969	996669966	669996999	669999666	996666699	669996696	966969999	966969669	699696996	699696699	966966996	699696666
699669699	699666969	966996996	966999666	699669696	966996966	669999969	669996699	996666999	996669966	669999966	996666696	699699999	699696696	966969966	966966999	699699669	966966666
669966966	996696969	669969666	996696996	996699669	669966999	666996696	999666699	666999666	999666999	666999966	666999969	696696666	969966696	696696699	969966966	969969969	696699999
999996966	666669696	666666996	666669669	999996669	999996999	999696696	666969966	666966999	999696699	999696669	999996666	666669966	666669999	666669666	666669966	999996699	999999999

In each case all the blocks of order 6 are magic squares with equal magic sums. The magic sums are given by

$$S_{18 \times 18}(6, 9) := 149999999985; \quad S_{6 \times 6}(6, 9) := 49999999995.$$

It is only upside-down magic square.

For more studied with different options, see the author's work [47, 48, 49].

3.5 Water Reflection Magic Squares

Below are few examples of magic square with **water reflection** property

- 4-Digits Magic Squares

Example 3.15. *Let's consider a magic square of order 18 with 4-digits (1,2,3,5) given by*

13 13	2235	2533	533 1	2332	3253	5333	3533	3352	3332	3235	3322	3525	5553	3323	2355	3 133	5223
3522	3 13 1	2232	2553	5333	2333	3555	3332	53 13	3235	3333	3225	5253	2323	3352	3323	1333	5535
3325	3222	3333	2233	2555	5332	2353	2335	553 1	3533	5323	1353	3323	35 13	3233	3 135	5232	3352
3 153	5325	3322	3232	2253	2552	5335	3333	5233	3323	5533	3523	323 1	3535	3332	1333	23 13	2355
3223	3353	5525	5322	3535	2255	25 13	3523	1332	2333	5235	3333	3332	3233	3 153	333 1	2352	5333
5332	3323	3253	5225	5522	3333	2252	3233	3 135	3335	1332	2333	3553	3355	3533	23 13	5323	253 1
3353	5535	5323	3553	1325	5222	2323	3335	3333	3532	3 133	3355	3252	3232	233 1	5333	2533	22 13
3335	3233	3523	3333	2335	3332	3533	2222	5323	2553	2325	3 132	1333	523 1	55 13	5352	3355	3253
5233	1353	3 155	3352	32 13	353 1	3333	2353	2525	5322	2223	5532	5335	3333	3223	3533	3335	2332
3233	3532	3335	2333	3323	3533	3235	5325	2253	2323	2522	333 1	3 1 13	1352	5255	5553	5333	3332
3532	3333	2353	3355	3552	32 13	333 1	2523	2322	2225	5353	3235	3333	3 123	1333	5235	5532	5333
2233	2532	53 13	2335	3333	3323	5533	323 1	3255	3 133	3532	5252	2322	3325	5353	3523	3353	1335
2535	5352	2333	3 132	3233	5335	5232	33 13	3553	133 1	3333	2223	5555	3322	2325	3353	3223	3533
5355	2323	1335	3535	3332	5533	3232	3 152	3333	52 13	233 1	2533	2233	5353	3522	3325	3253	3323
2333	5233	3332	3233	533 1	3335	3 123	1355	2332	5552	33 13	5353	2523	2235	3333	3222	3525	3553
5523	2333	353 1	33 13	3 133	1323	3353	5253	3335	5355	3552	2335	5333	2533	2232	3232	3322	3225
333 1	33 13	3252	1323	5223	2353	3325	5533	3533	3353	3255	5333	2332	5332	2535	2233	3535	3 122
2352	3555	5233	5523	3353	3 125	1322	5332	3223	3233	3353	35 13	3335	2333	5335	2532	223 1	3333

The magic sum of above magic square is given as $S_{18 \times 18}(1, 2, 3, 5) = 62216$.

Example 3.16. Let's consider a magic square of order 18 with 5-digits (2,3,5,8) given by

2222	3355	3353	3523	3353	2552	5283	3223	5335	2325	5332	8333	5533	3835	3233	3338	2332	3533
5533	2323	3353	3352	3523	3353	3238	3225	5222	2532	5332	5333	3535	3333	8335	2333	2283	3855
5333	5333	2323	3353	3338	3525	3352	3332	3823	3232	5233	2235	8333	5522	2583	2355	3553	3235
2335	5233	5333	2525	3352	3335	3532	8332	3523	3233	3883	5533	5323	3255	2353	2253	3322	3338
5333	2335	3833	5233	3232	3338	3322	5533	2225	3383	3555	5323	3253	2553	2352	8323	3335	3532
5225	5333	2535	3533	3833	3232	3335	5383	2332	8355	2253	3353	3252	2338	5523	3322	3533	3323
8352	3832	5233	3235	2233	3533	3333	5355	2332	5553	2353	3238	2535	5325	3323	3583	3323	3322
2332	2532	3233	3283	3355	8353	5553	3333	3533	3335	3333	2325	2223	3523	3822	5235	5338	5352
3553	2252	2338	2335	2522	3223	3223	3335	3333	3533	3333	3853	5255	5383	5333	5532	8332	3325
2523	3225	3232	3332	8333	5583	5355	3533	3335	3333	3333	2323	2322	2235	3538	3852	5253	5353
3253	3253	3352	8338	5535	5322	5323	3333	3333	3333	3535	2555	2383	2333	2232	3532	3825	5223
3383	3353	3522	3355	2353	5333	3832	2523	5338	2323	5525	3535	3333	8333	5235	3233	3252	2232
3355	3535	3383	2353	5332	5232	3525	2322	5552	2223	8323	3333	3838	3233	3333	5335	2533	3253
3538	3333	2255	5532	5325	3823	2553	2335	8353	3522	3323	3383	3332	5252	3233	3233	5335	2333
3332	3583	8325	5323	5223	2355	2333	2238	3353	3835	3222	3552	3333	3332	5353	2533	3233	5535
3833	3323	5523	5322	2383	2233	8335	3552	3255	5238	3235	3332	3553	3332	3325	5353	2333	2533
3223	8322	5335	2233	3533	3335	2333	3853	3283	5352	2538	5232	3325	3553	3332	3323	5555	2333
3335	5538	3532	3833	3235	2333	2233	5253	2533	5353	2352	3222	5332	3323	3555	3325	3323	8383

The magic sum of above magic square is given as $S_{18 \times 18}(2, 3, 5, 8) = 69993$.

The magic squares given in Examples 3.15 and 3.16 are with **water reflection** property

• **3-Digits Magic Squares**

Example 3.17. *Let's consider a magic square of order 18 with 3-digits (2,3,5) given by*

222222	322553	332535	353225	335552	233533	533555	252232	535522	232233	552252	555322	553332	525353	253335	255525	225253	522255
553322	225225	322552	332533	353232	335535	252525	253233	533222	233252	535253	552332	522353	255335	555522	232255	222555	525553
535332	552322	232232	322535	332525	353233	335533	255252	525225	252253	533255	222353	555335	553222	233555	225553	522552	253522
225353	533332	535322	233233	322533	332522	353252	555253	522232	253255	525555	553335	552225	252553	232552	222535	255222	335525
552335	232353	525332	533322	252252	322525	332222	553255	222233	255555	522553	535232	253552	233535	225533	555225	335522	353253
533233	535335	233353	522332	525322	253253	322522	552555	225252	555553	222552	255535	252533	232525	553232	335222	353255	332225
555533	525252	533335	252353	222332	522322	255255	535553	232253	553552	225535	253525	233522	552233	335225	353555	332232	322222
232252	233253	252255	253555	255553	555552	553535	322322	353335	332353	335332	225233	222232	522225	525222	533522	535525	552533
522535	222533	225525	232522	233222	252225	253232	335353	332332	353322	322335	525552	533553	535555	552255	553253	555252	255233
233232	252233	253252	255253	555255	553555	552553	353332	322353	335335	332322	232225	225222	222522	522525	525533	533535	535552
252552	253535	255533	555525	553522	552222	535225	332335	335322	322332	353353	233553	232555	225255	222253	522252	525233	533232
322555	332552	353222	335553	232535	535255	525253	233225	552525	225232	553233	522522	255322	555332	533353	252335	253533	222252
332553	353522	335555	225552	552253	533252	522233	232222	553533	222225	555232	322255	525525	253322	255332	535353	233335	252535
353525	335255	222553	553252	535233	525232	233552	225522	555535	522222	255225	332555	322253	533533	252322	253332	552353	232335
335253	522555	555233	552232	533225	232553	225335	222525	255552	525522	253222	353533	332255	322252	535535	233322	252332	553353
525255	255232	553225	535222	225555	222335	555353	522533	253553	533525	252522	335252	353535	332253	322233	552552	232322	233332
253225	555222	552522	222255	522335	255353	232332	525535	252555	535533	233525	533253	335233	353552	332252	322232	553553	225322
255522	553525	522253	525335	253353	225332	222322	533552	233255	552535	232533	252222	535252	335232	353553	332233	322225	555555

The magic sum of above magic square is given as $S_{18 \times 18}(2, 3, 5) = 6795789$.

Example 3.18. *Let's consider a magic square of order 18 with 3-digits (1,3,8) given by*

111111	311883	331838	383118	338881	133833	833888	181131	838811	131133	881181	888311	883331	818383	183338	188818	118183	811188
883311	118118	311881	331833	383131	338838	181818	183133	833111	133181	838183	881331	811383	188338	888811	131188	111888	818883
838331	881311	131131	311838	331818	383133	338833	188181	818118	181183	833188	111383	888338	883111	133888	118883	811881	183811
118383	833331	838311	133133	311833	331811	383181	888183	811131	183188	818888	883338	881118	181883	131881	111838	188111	338818
881338	131383	818331	833311	181181	311818	331111	883188	111133	188888	811883	838131	183881	133838	118833	888118	338811	383183
833133	838338	133383	811331	818311	183183	311811	881888	118181	888883	111881	188838	181833	131818	883131	338111	383188	331118
888833	818181	833338	181383	111331	811311	188188	838883	131183	883881	118838	183818	133811	881133	338118	383888	331131	311111
131181	133183	181188	183888	188883	888881	883838	311311	383338	331383	338331	118133	111131	811118	818111	833811	838818	881833
811838	111833	118818	131811	133111	181118	183131	338383	331331	383311	311338	818881	833883	838888	881188	883183	888181	188133
133131	181133	183181	188183	888188	883888	881883	383331	311383	338338	331311	131118	118111	111811	811818	818833	833838	838881
181881	183838	188833	888818	883811	881111	838118	331338	338311	311331	383383	133883	131888	118188	111183	811181	818133	833131
311888	331881	383111	338883	131838	838188	818183	133118	881818	118131	883133	811811	188311	888331	833383	181338	183833	111181
331883	383811	338888	118881	881183	833181	811133	131111	883833	111118	888131	311188	818818	183311	188331	838383	133338	181838
383818	338188	111883	883181	838133	818131	133881	118811	888838	811111	188118	331888	311183	833833	181311	183331	881383	131338
338183	811888	888133	881131	833118	131883	118338	111818	188881	818811	183111	383833	331188	311181	838838	133311	181331	883383
818188	188131	883118	838111	118888	111338	888383	811833	183883	833818	181811	338181	383838	331183	311133	881881	131311	133331
183118	888111	881811	111188	811338	188383	131331	818838	181888	838833	133818	833183	338133	383881	331181	311131	883883	118311
188811	883818	811183	818338	183383	118331	111311	833881	133188	881838	131833	181111	838181	338131	383883	331133	311118	888888

The magic sum of above magic square is given as $S_{18 \times 18}(1, 3, 8) = 8368360$.

The magic squares given in Examples 3.17 and 3.18 are with **water reflection** property

• **2-Digits Magic Squares**

Example 3.19. *Let's consider a magic square of order 18 with 2-digits (1,3) given by*

111311131	133311131	311313331	313111111	311113333	113313311	331113313	131311131	333113131	113111131	333311313	331331331	113113113	331313131	131113111	133113313	111113111	313311331
113111333	111111111	133313333	311313311	313111131	311113331	131313313	131111331	331111131	113311313	333113111	333313113	313313131	133113111	331333131	113111331	111313313	331311331
333113113	333311333	113111131	133313331	311313313	313111133	311113311	133111313	331311111	131311311	331111331	111313131	331333111	113111131	113313313	111111311	313313333	131113133
111113131	331113113	333111333	113311133	133313311	311313331	313111313	331331311	313311131	131111331	331333133	113113111	333311111	131311131	113113333	111313331	133111131	311113313
333313111	113113131	331313113	331111333	131311313	133313313	311311131	113111331	111311133	133113313	313311131	333111311	131113333	113313331	111113311	331331111	311113333	313111311
331111331	333113111	113313131	313313113	331313331	131111311	133313133	333313313	111113131	331331131	111313333	133113331	131313311	113113313	113111311	311111131	313113311	311311111
331333311	331311313	331113111	131313131	111313131	313311333	133111331	333111131	113113111	113113333	111113331	131113313	113313331	333311133	311111111	313113313	311311131	133311131
113111313	113311311	131311331	131113313	133111131	331333331	113113331	133311333	313113111	311313131	311113113	111111331	111311131	313311111	331311131	331113331	333113313	333313311
313313331	111333111	111113313	113113331	113311131	131311111	131111131	311113131	311313131	313113331	133313111	331313333	331111131	333113313	333311331	113111311	331331313	133111331
113311131	131311133	131111313	133111311	331331331	113113313	333311131	313113131	133313131	311113111	311311333	113111111	111111131	111313331	313313313	331333111	331113331	333113333
131313333	131113331	133113311	331333313	113113133	333311113	333111111	311313111	311113331	133313113	313113131	113311131	113113313	111113331	111313111	313311313	331311331	331111311
133313313	311313333	313111131	311111131	113113331	333111331	331311311	113311111	333313313	111111131	113111331	313313331	133113331	331333113	331113131	131313111	131113311	111311313
311311131	313113133	311113313	111113333	333311311	331111313	313311133	113111131	113113311	111311111	331331131	133311331	331313313	131113331	133113131	333113131	113311111	131313331
313113313	311111331	111311131	113111313	333111133	331311131	113313331	111113333	331333311	313311131	133111111	311313313	133311311	331113311	131313331	131113131	333313131	113113111
311111311	313313313	331331133	333311131	331111111	113111131	111113111	111313313	133113333	331313133	131111131	313113311	311311331	133311313	333113331	113311333	131313131	113113131
331311331	133111131	113111111	333111131	111113313	111313111	331333131	313313311	131111311	331113313	131313331	311113131	313113331	311311311	133311133	333313331	113111333	113313131
131111111	331331113	333313133	111311331	313313111	133113131	113113131	331313331	131313313	333113311	113313313	331111311	311111331	313113333	311313331	133311131	113111311	111113331
133113133	113113313	313311311	331313111	131113131	111113131	111311333	331113333	113311331	333313331	113113311	131311131	333111313	311111313	313111331	313113333	311313331	133311111

The magic sum of above magic square is given as $S_{18 \times 18}(1,3) = 39998399980$.

Example 3.20. Let's consider a magic square of order 18 with 2-digits (3,8) given by

8883888838	8333888388	3883833388	3838888888	3888833338	8833833888	3388833833	8383888388	3338838338	8838888338	3338883838	3383383338	8838838838	3383838388	8388838888	8338833838	8888838888	3833883388
8838883338	8888888888	8333833338	3883833888	3838888388	3888833388	8383833838	8388888338	3388888838	8833883838	3338883888	3338838838	3838838888	8338838888	3383338338	8888888388	8883833833	3383888388
3338838838	3338883338	8838888388	8333833388	3883833838	3838888338	3888833888	8338883838	3383888888	8383883888	3388883388	8883838888	8838838838	3383388888	8838833833	8888888388	3833833338	8388838338
8888838838	3388838838	3338883338	8833888338	8333833888	3883838338	3838888388	3383383888	3833888388	8388883388	3383833833	8838838888	3338888888	8383888388	8838833338	8883833888	8338888888	3888838838
3333838888	8838838838	3383838838	3388883338	8383888388	8333833838	3883888388	8838883888	8883888338	8338833833	3833888388	3338888888	8383888388	8838833338	8888838888	3383388888	3888838338	3838883888
3388888338	3338838888	8833838838	3833838838	3383888338	8388883888	8333838338	3333833833	8888888388	3383388388	8883833338	8338833888	8838883888	8888838888	8838838838	3888888388	3838883888	3883888888
3383338888	3383888388	3388838888	8383838888	8883838838	3833888338	8338883888	3338888388	8838883888	8838833338	8888833888	8388838838	8833838838	3333888338	3888888888	3838833833	3883888388	8333888838
8838883838	8833888388	8383888388	8388833833	8338888388	3383333338	8838833888	8333888338	3838838888	3883838888	3888838838	8888888338	8883888388	3833888888	3383888388	3388838338	3338833888	3333833888
3833833888	8883838888	8888833838	8838838338	8833888838	8383888888	8388888388	3888838888	3883838888	3838883338	8333838888	3383833338	3388888388	3333888338	8838883888	3383838888	8338888338	8338888338
8833888388	8383888338	8388883838	8338888888	3383383888	8838833833	3333888388	3838838838	8333838888	3888838888	3883883338	8838888888	8888888388	8883838838	3833838838	3383838888	3388833888	3338833338
8383833338	8388833888	8338838888	3383338838	8838838338	3333888838	3338888888	3883838888	3888883338	8333838838	3838838888	8838888888	8888888388	8883838838	3833838838	3383838888	3388833888	3388888388
8333833833	3883833338	3838888838	3888888388	8838833888	3338888388	3383888888	8833888888	3333833838	8888888388	8838888338	3833838838	8338888338	3383388838	3388838888	8383838888	8388838888	8883888388
3883888388	3838838838	3888833833	8888833338	3333888888	3388888388	3833888338	8838888838	8838838888	8883888888	3383388388	8333888388	3383838838	8388883338	8338838838	3388838888	8383838888	8383833888
3838838838	3888883388	8883888388	8838888388	3338888338	3383888388	8833833338	8888838838	3383333888	3833888838	8338888888	3883838833	8333888888	3388838888	8383888338	8388838888	3333838888	8838838888
3888883888	3833833833	3383388338	3333888388	3388888888	8838888388	8888838888	8883833838	8338883338	3383838838	8388888838	3838838888	3883888388	8338883888	3338883388	8838883338	8383838838	8838838888
3383883388	8338888388	8838888888	3338888838	8888833833	8883838888	3383338888	3833838888	8388888888	3388838838	8383838838	3888883838	3883888388	8338888388	3338883338	8838883338	8838883388	8833838838
8388888888	3383388838	3333838838	8883888388	3833838888	8338838888	8838838838	3383833888	8383838833	3338838888	8833838838	3388883888	3883888338	3888888388	3883888338	3888883838	8888883338	8888883338
8338838838	8838838838	3833888888	3383838888	8388838888	8888838838	8883883338	3388833338	8833883888	3333833888	8838838888	8383888838	3338888388	3888888388	3883888388	3888883838	8338888888	3383338833

The magic sum of above magic square is given as $S_{18 \times 18}(3, 8) = 110004000029$.

The magic squares given in Examples 3.19 and 3.20 are with **water reflection** property.

For more studied with different options, see the author's work [47, 48, 49].

3.6 Self-Made Algebraic Magic Square

Below is a result of a magic square order 18 made from the variables A1 to A128 and a magic sum.

Result 1. Below is an algebraic magic square of order 18

$(1/2)*S-A112$	$A99+A98+A97+A111-A113+A110+A108+A109+A107+A105+A106+A103+A104+A102+A100+A101+A112-(7/2)*S$	$(1/2)*S-A97$	$(1/2)*S-A98$	$(1/2)*S-A99$	$(1/2)*S-A100$	$(1/2)*S-A101$	$(1/2)*S-A102$	$(1/2)*S-A103$	$(1/2)*S-A104$	$(1/2)*S-A105$	$(1/2)*S-A106$	$(1/2)*S-A107$	$(1/2)*S-A108$	$(1/2)*S-A109$	$(1/2)*S-A110$	$(1/2)*S-A111$	A113
$(1/2)*S-A114$	A1	$A4+S-A6-A1$	$A6-A3-A4$	A3	A7	$A10+S-A12-A7$	$A12-A9-A10$	A9	A13	$A16+S-A18-A13$	$A18-A15-A16$	A15	A19	$A22+S-A24-A19$	$A24-A21-A22$	A21	A114
$(1/2)*S-A115$	A6	A4	A5	$S-A4-A5-A6$	A12	A10	A11	$S-A10-A11-A12$	A18	A16	A17	$S-A16-A17-A18$	A24	A22	A23	$S-A22-A23-A24$	A115
$(1/2)*S-A116$	$A2+A3-A6$	$A1+A2-A5$	$S-A1-A2-A4$	$A4+A5+A6-A2-A3$	$A8+A9-A12$	$A7+A8-A11$	$S-A7-A8-A10$	$A10+A11+A12-A8-A9$	$A14+A15-A18$	$A13+A14-A17$	$S-A13-A14-A16$	$A16+A17+A18-A14-A15$	$A20+A21-A24$	$A19+A20-A23$	$S-A19-A20-A22$	$A22+A23+A24-A20-A21$	A116
$(1/2)*S-A117$	$S-A1-A2-A3$	$A5-A2-2*A4+A6$	$A1+A2+A3+2*A4-A5-A6$	A2	$S-A7-A8-A9$	$A11-A8-2*A10+A12$	$A7+A8+A9+2*A10-A11-A12$	A8	$S-A13-A14-A15$	$A17-A14-2*A16+A18$	$A13+A14+A15+2*A16-A17-A18$	A14	$S-A19-A20-A21$	$A23-A20-2*A22+A24$	$A19+A20+A21+2*A22-A23-A24$	A20	A117
$(1/2)*S-A118$	A25	$A28+S-A30-A25$	$A30-A27-A28$	A27	A31	$A34+S-A36-A31$	$A36-A33-A34$	A33	A37	$A40+S-A42-A37$	$A42-A39-A40$	A39	A43	$A46+S-A48-A43$	$A48-A45-A46$	A45	A118
$(1/2)*S-A119$	A30	A28	A29	$S-A28-A29-A30$	A36	A34	A35	$S-A34-A35-A36$	A42	A40	A41	$S-A40-A41-A42$	A48	A46	A47	$S-A46-A47-A48$	A119
$(1/2)*S-A120$	$A26+A27-A30$	$A25+A26-A29$	$S-A25-A26-A28$	$A28+A29+A30-A26-A27$	$A32+A33-A36$	$A31+A32-A35$	$S-A31-A32-A34$	$A34+A35+A36-A32-A33$	$A38+A39-A42$	$A37+A38-A41$	$S-A37-A38-A40$	$A40+A41+A42-A38-A39$	$A44+A45-A48$	$A43+A44-A47$	$S-A43-A44-A46$	$A46+A47+A48-A44-A45$	A120
$(1/2)*S-A121$	$S-A25-A26-A27$	$A29-A26-2*A28+A30$	$A25+A26+A27+2*A28-A29-A30$	A26	$S-A31-A32-A33$	$A35-A32-2*A34+A36$	$A31+A32+A33+2*A34-A35-A36$	A32	$S-A37-A38-A39$	$A41-A38-2*A40+A42$	$A37+A38+A39+2*A40-A41-A42$	A38	$S-A43-A44-A45$	$A47-A44-2*A46+A48$	$A43+A44+A45+2*A46-A47-A48$	A44	A121
$(1/2)*S-A122$	A49	$A52+S-A54-A49$	$A54-A51-A52$	A51	A55	$A58+S-A60-A55$	$A60-A57-A58$	A57	A61	$A64+S-A66-A61$	$A66-A63-A64$	A63	A67	$A70+S-A72-A67$	$A72-A69-A70$	A69	A122
$(1/2)*S-A123$	A54	A52	A53	$S-A52-A53-A54$	A60	A58	A59	$S-A58-A59-A60$	A66	A64	A65	$S-A64-A65-A66$	A72	A70	A71	$S-A70-A71-A72$	A123
$(1/2)*S-A124$	$A50+A51-A54$	$A49+A50-A53$	$S-A49-A50-A52$	$A52+A53+A54-A50-A51$	$A56+A57-A60$	$A55+A56-A59$	$S-A55-A56-A58$	$A58+A59+A60-A56-A57$	$A62+A63-A66$	$A61+A62-A65$	$S-A61-A62-A64$	$A64+A65+A66-A62-A63$	$A68+A69-A72$	$A67+A68-A71$	$S-A67-A68-A70$	$A70+A71+A72-A68-A69$	A124
$(1/2)*S-A125$	$S-A49-A50-A51$	$A53-A50-2*A52+A54$	$A49+A50+A51+2*A52-A53-A54$	A50	$S-A55-A56-A57$	$A59-A56-2*A58+A60$	$A55+A56+A57+2*A58-A59-A60$	A56	$S-A61-A62-A63$	$A65-A62-2*A64+A66$	$A61+A62+A63+2*A64-A65-A66$	A62	$S-A67-A68-A69$	$A71-A68-2*A70+A72$	$A67+A68+A69+2*A70-A71-A72$	A68	A125
$(1/2)*S-A126$	A73	$A76+S-A78-A73$	$A78-A75-A76$	A75	A79	$A82+S-A84-A79$	$A84-A81-A82$	A81	A85	$A88+S-A90-A85$	$A90-A87-A88$	A87	A91	$A94+S-A96-A91$	$A96-A93-A94$	A93	A126
$(1/2)*S-A127$	A78	A76	A77	$S-A76-A77-A78$	A84	A82	A83	$S-A82-A83-A84$	A90	A88	A89	$S-A88-A89-A90$	A96	A94	A95	$S-A94-A95-A96$	A127
$(1/2)*S-A128$	$A74+A75-A78$	$A73+A74-A77$	$S-A73-A74-A76$	$A76+A77+A78-A74-A75$	$A80+A81-A84$	$A79+A80-A83$	$S-A79-A80-A82$	$A82+A83+A84-A80-A81$	$A86+A87-A90$	$A85+A86-A89$	$S-A85-A86-A88$	$A88+A89+A90-A86-A87$	$A92+A93-A96$	$A91+A92-A95$	$S-A91-A92-A94$	$A94+A95+A96-A92-A93$	A128
$A113+A114+A115+A116+A117+A118+A119+A120+A121+A122+A123+A124+A125+A126+A127+A128+A112-4*S$	$S-A73-A74-A75$	$A77-A74-2*A76+A78$	$A73+A74+A75+2*A76-A77-A78$	A74	$S-A79-A80-A81$	$A83-A80-2*A82+A84$	$A79+A80+A81+2*A82-A83-A84$	A80	$S-A85-A86-A87$	$A89-A86-2*A88+A90$	$A85+A86+A87+2*A88-A89-A90$	A86	$S-A91-A92-A93$	$A95-A92-2*A94+A96$	$A91+A92+A93+2*A94-A95-A96$	A92	$9*S/2-A113-A114-A115-A116-A117-A118-A119-A120-A121-A122-A123-A124-A125-A126-A127-A128-A112$
$(1/2)*S-A113$	$4*S-A99-A98-A97-A111+A113-A110-A108-A109-A107-A105-A106-A103-A104-A102-A100-A101-A112$	A97	A98	A99	A100	A101	A102	A103	A104	A105	A106	A107	A108	A109	A110	A111	A112

● **Details**

It is **single-digits bordered** magic square of order 18 embedded with a magic square of order 16 formed by equal sums magic sums of order 4. We call it a **self-made** as choosing any numbers for A1 to A128 and the magic sum S, we always get a magic square of order 18. Sometimes we may call it as **algebraic magic square for reduced entries**. It requires only 96 entries instead of 324. See below two examples:

Example 3.21. Let's consider a following magic square based on the Result 1

mgc	18x18	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	https://numbers-magic.com/	@IJTANEJA	©IJT	207												
-90	1413	-75	-76	-77	-78	-79	-80	-81	-82	-83	-84	-85	-86	-87	-88	-89	114	207
-92	2	42	-2	4	8	36	-8	10	14	30	-14	16	20	24	-20	22	115	207
-93	7	5	6	28	13	11	12	10	19	17	18	-8	25	23	24	-26	116	207
-94	0	-1	36	11	6	5	18	17	12	11	0	23	18	17	-18	29	117	207
-95	37	0	6	3	19	-6	24	9	1	-12	42	15	-17	-18	60	21	118	207
-96	26	18	-26	28	32	12	-32	34	38	6	-38	40	44	0	-44	46	119	207
-97	31	29	30	-44	37	35	36	-62	43	41	42	-80	49	47	48	-98	120	207
-98	24	23	-36	35	30	29	-54	41	36	35	-72	47	42	41	-90	53	121	207
-99	-35	-24	78	27	-53	-30	96	33	-71	-36	114	39	-89	-42	132	45	122	207
-100	50	-6	-50	52	56	-12	-56	58	62	-18	-62	64	68	-24	-68	70	123	207
-101	55	53	54	-116	61	59	60	-134	67	65	66	-152	73	71	72	-170	124	207
-102	48	47	-108	59	54	53	-126	65	60	59	-144	71	66	65	-162	77	125	207
-103	-107	-48	150	51	-125	-54	168	57	-143	-60	186	63	-161	-66	204	69	126	207
-104	74	-30	-74	76	80	-36	-80	82	86	-42	-86	88	92	-48	-92	94	127	207
-105	79	77	78	-188	85	83	84	-206	91	89	90	-224	97	95	96	-242	128	207
-106	72	71	-180	83	78	77	-198	89	84	83	-216	95	90	89	-234	101	129	207
1873	-179	-72	222	75	-197	-78	240	81	-215	-84	258	87	-233	-90	276	93	-1850	207
-91	-1390	98	99	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108	109	110	111	112	113	207
207	207	207	207	207	207	207	207	207	207	207	207	207	207	207	207	207	207	207

It is **single-digits bordered** magic square of order 18 embedded with a magic square of order 16 formed by equal sums magic sums of order 4.

Example 3.22. *Let's consider a following magic square based on the Result 1*

mgc	18x18	https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/	https://numbers-magic.com/	@IJTANEJA	©IJT	216												
-89	1406	-74	-75	-76	-77	-78	-79	-80	-81	-82	-83	-84	-85	-86	-87	-88	114	216
-91	2	44	-2	4	8	38	-8	10	14	32	-14	16	20	26	-20	22	115	216
-92	7	5	6	30	13	11	12	12	19	17	18	-6	25	23	24	-24	116	216
-93	0	-1	38	11	6	5	20	17	12	11	2	23	18	17	-16	29	117	216
-94	39	0	6	3	21	-6	24	9	3	-12	42	15	-15	-18	60	21	118	216
-95	26	20	-26	28	32	14	-32	34	38	8	-38	40	44	2	-44	46	119	216
-96	31	29	30	-42	37	35	36	-60	43	41	42	-78	49	47	48	-96	120	216
-97	24	23	-34	35	30	29	-52	41	36	35	-70	47	42	41	-88	53	121	216
-98	-33	-24	78	27	-51	-30	96	33	-69	-36	114	39	-87	-42	132	45	122	216
-99	50	-4	-50	52	56	-10	-56	58	62	-16	-62	64	68	-22	-68	70	123	216
-100	55	53	54	-114	61	59	60	-132	67	65	66	-150	73	71	72	-168	124	216
-101	48	47	-106	59	54	53	-124	65	60	59	-142	71	66	65	-160	77	125	216
-102	-105	-48	150	51	-123	-54	168	57	-141	-60	186	63	-159	-66	204	69	126	216
-103	74	-28	-74	76	80	-34	-80	82	86	-40	-86	88	92	-46	-92	94	127	216
-104	79	77	78	-186	85	83	84	-204	91	89	90	-222	97	95	96	-240	128	216
-105	72	71	-178	83	78	77	-196	89	84	83	-214	95	90	89	-232	101	129	216
1865	-177	-72	222	75	-195	-78	240	81	-213	-84	258	87	-231	-90	276	93	-1841	216
-90	-1382	98	99	100	101	102	103	104	105	106	107	108	109	110	111	112	113	216
216	216	216	216	216	216	216	216	216	216	216	216	216	216	216	216	216	216	216

It is single-digits bordered magic square of order 18 embedded with a magic square of order 16 formed by equal sums magic sums of order 4.

Below is a result of a magic square order 18 made from the variables A1 to A72 and a magic sum with equal sum magic squares of order 3.

Result 2. *Below is an algebraic magic square of order 18*

$a1+a2-S/3$	$2*S/3-a2$	$2*S/3-a1$	$a3+a4-S/3$	$2*S/3-a4$	$2*S/3-a3$	$a5+a6-S/3$	$2*S/3-a6$	$2*S/3-a5$	$a7+a8-S/3$	$2*S/3-a8$	$2*S/3-a7$	$a9+a10-S/3$	$2*S/3-a10$	$2*S/3-a9$	$a11+a12-S/3$	$2*S/3-a12$	$2*S/3-a11$
$4*S/3-2*a1-a2$	$S/3$	$2*a1+a2-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a3-a4$	$S/3$	$2*a3+a4-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a5-a6$	$S/3$	$2*a5+a6-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a7-a8$	$S/3$	$2*a7+a8-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a9-a10$	$S/3$	$2*a9+a10-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a11-a12$	$S/3$	$2*a11+a12-2*S/3$
a1	a2	S-a1-a2	a3	a4	S-a3-a4	a5	a6	S-a5-a6	a7	a8	S-a7-a8	a9	a10	S-a9-a10	a11	a12	S-a11-a12
$a13+a14-S/3$	$2*S/3-a14$	$2*S/3-a13$	$a15+a16-S/3$	$2*S/3-a16$	$2*S/3-a15$	$a17+a18-S/3$	$2*S/3-a18$	$2*S/3-a17$	$a19+a20-S/3$	$2*S/3-a20$	$2*S/3-a19$	$a21+a22-S/3$	$2*S/3-a22$	$2*S/3-a21$	$a23+a24-S/3$	$2*S/3-a24$	$2*S/3-a23$
$4*S/3-2*a13-a14$	$S/3$	$2*a13+a14-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a15-a16$	$S/3$	$2*a15+a16-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a17-a18$	$S/3$	$2*a17+a18-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a19-a20$	$S/3$	$2*a19+a20-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a21-a22$	$S/3$	$2*a21+a22-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a23-a24$	$S/3$	$2*a23+a24-2*S/3$
a13	a14	S-a13-a14	a15	a16	S-a15-a16	a17	a18	S-a17-a18	a19	a20	S-a19-a20	a21	a22	S-a21-a22	a23	a24	S-a23-a24
$a25+a26-S/3$	$2*S/3-a26$	$2*S/3-a25$	$a27+a28-S/3$	$2*S/3-a28$	$2*S/3-a27$	$a29+a30-S/3$	$2*S/3-a30$	$2*S/3-a29$	$a31+a32-S/3$	$2*S/3-a32$	$2*S/3-a31$	$a33+a34-S/3$	$2*S/3-a34$	$2*S/3-a33$	$a35+a36-S/3$	$2*S/3-a36$	$2*S/3-a35$
$4*S/3-2*a25-a26$	$S/3$	$2*a25+a26-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a27-a28$	$S/3$	$2*a27+a28-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a29-a30$	$S/3$	$2*a29+a30-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a31-a32$	$S/3$	$2*a31+a32-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a33-a34$	$S/3$	$2*a33+a34-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a35-a36$	$S/3$	$2*a35+a36-2*S/3$
a25	a26	S-a25-a26	a27	a28	S-a27-a28	a29	a30	S-a29-a30	a31	a32	S-a31-a32	a33	a34	S-a33-a34	a35	a36	S-a35-a36
$a37+a38-S/3$	$2*S/3-a38$	$2*S/3-a37$	$a39+a40-S/3$	$2*S/3-a40$	$2*S/3-a39$	$a41+a42-S/3$	$2*S/3-a42$	$2*S/3-a41$	$a43+a44-S/3$	$2*S/3-a44$	$2*S/3-a43$	$a45+a46-S/3$	$2*S/3-a46$	$2*S/3-a45$	$a47+a48-S/3$	$2*S/3-a48$	$2*S/3-a47$
$4*S/3-2*a37-a38$	$S/3$	$2*a37+a38-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a39-a40$	$S/3$	$2*a39+a40-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a41-a42$	$S/3$	$2*a41+a42-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a43-a44$	$S/3$	$2*a43+a44-4-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a45-a46$	$S/3$	$2*a45+a46-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a47-a48$	$S/3$	$2*a47+a48-2*S/3$
a37	a38	S-a37-a38	a39	a40	S-a39-a40	a41	a42	S-a41-a42	a43	a44	S-a43-a44	a45	a46	S-a45-a46	a47	a48	S-a47-a48
$a49+a50-S/3$	$2*S/3-a50$	$2*S/3-a49$	$a51+a52-S/3$	$2*S/3-a52$	$2*S/3-a51$	$a53+a54-S/3$	$2*S/3-a54$	$2*S/3-a53$	$a55+a56-S/3$	$2*S/3-a56$	$2*S/3-a55$	$a57+a58-S/3$	$2*S/3-a58$	$2*S/3-a57$	$a59+a60-S/3$	$2*S/3-a60$	$2*S/3-a59$
$4*S/3-2*a49-a50$	$S/3$	$2*a49+a50-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a51-a52$	$S/3$	$2*a51+a52-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a53-a54$	$S/3$	$2*a53+a54-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a55-a56$	$S/3$	$2*a55+a56-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a57-a58$	$S/3$	$2*a57+a58-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a59-a60$	$S/3$	$2*a59+a60-2*S/3$
a49	a50	S-a49-a50	a51	a52	S-a51-a52	a53	a54	S-a53-a54	a55	a56	S-a55-a56	a57	a58	S-a57-a58	a59	a60	S-a59-a60
$a61+a62-S/3$	$2*S/3-a62$	$2*S/3-a61$	$a63+a64-S/3$	$2*S/3-a64$	$2*S/3-a63$	$a65+a66-S/3$	$2*S/3-a66$	$2*S/3-a65$	$a67+a68-S/3$	$2*S/3-a68$	$2*S/3-a67$	$a69+a70-S/3$	$2*S/3-a70$	$2*S/3-a69$	$a71+a72-S/3$	$2*S/3-a72$	$2*S/3-a71$
$4*S/3-2*a61-a62$	$S/3$	$2*a61+a62-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a63-a64$	$S/3$	$2*a63+a64-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a65-a66$	$S/3$	$2*a65+a66-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a67-a68$	$S/3$	$2*a67+a68-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a69-a70$	$S/3$	$2*a69+a70-2*S/3$	$4*S/3-2*a71-a72$	$S/3$	$2*a71+a72-2*S/3$
a61	a62	S-a61-a62	a63	a64	S-a63-a64	a65	a66	S-a65-a66	a67	a68	S-a67-a68	a69	a70	S-a69-a70	a71	a72	S-a71-a72

It is a **self-made** magic square of order 18 formed by equal sums magic squares of order 3. It requires only 72 entries instead of 324. See below two examples:

Example 3.23. *Let's consider a following magic square based on the Result 2*

mgc	18x18 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA ©IJT																	198
-8	20	21	-4	18	19	0	16	17	4	14	15	8	12	13	12	10	11	198
40	11	-18	34	11	-12	28	11	-6	22	11	0	16	11	6	10	11	12	198
1	2	30	3	4	26	5	6	22	7	8	18	9	10	14	11	12	10	198
16	8	9	20	6	7	24	4	5	28	2	3	32	0	1	36	-2	-1	198
4	11	18	-2	11	24	-8	11	30	-14	11	36	-20	11	42	-26	11	48	198
13	14	6	15	16	2	17	18	-2	19	20	-6	21	22	-10	23	24	-14	198
40	-4	-3	44	-6	-5	48	-8	-7	52	-10	-9	56	-12	-11	60	-14	-13	198
-32	11	54	-38	11	60	-44	11	66	-50	11	72	-56	11	78	-62	11	84	198
25	26	-18	27	28	-22	29	30	-26	31	32	-30	33	34	-34	35	36	-38	198
64	-16	-15	68	-18	-17	72	-20	-19	76	-22	-21	80	-24	-23	84	-26	-25	198
-68	11	90	-74	11	96	-80	11	102	-86	11	108	-92	11	114	-98	11	120	198
37	38	-42	39	40	-46	41	42	-50	43	44	-54	45	46	-58	47	48	-62	198
88	-28	-27	92	-30	-29	96	-32	-31	100	-34	-33	104	-36	-35	108	-38	-37	198
-104	11	126	-110	11	132	-116	11	138	-122	11	144	-128	11	150	-134	11	156	198
49	50	-66	51	52	-70	53	54	-74	55	56	-78	57	58	-82	59	60	-86	198
112	-40	-39	116	-42	-41	120	-44	-43	124	-46	-45	128	-48	-47	132	-50	-49	198
-140	11	162	-146	11	168	-152	11	174	-158	11	180	-164	11	186	-170	11	192	198
61	62	-90	63	64	-94	65	66	-98	67	68	-102	69	70	-106	71	72	-110	198
198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198	198

It is a self-made magic square of order 18 formed by equal sums magic squares of order 3.

Example 3.24. *Let's consider a following magic square based on the Result 2*

mgc	18x18 https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA ©IJT																	216
-9	22	23	-5	20	21	-1	18	19	3	16	17	7	14	15	11	12	13	216
44	12	-20	38	12	-14	32	12	-8	26	12	-2	20	12	4	14	12	10	216
1	2	33	3	4	29	5	6	25	7	8	21	9	10	17	11	12	13	216
15	10	11	19	8	9	23	6	7	27	4	5	31	2	3	35	0	1	216
8	12	16	2	12	22	-4	12	28	-10	12	34	-16	12	40	-22	12	46	216
13	14	9	15	16	5	17	18	1	19	20	-3	21	22	-7	23	24	-11	216
39	-2	-1	43	-4	-3	47	-6	-5	51	-8	-7	55	-10	-9	59	-12	-11	216
-28	12	52	-34	12	58	-40	12	64	-46	12	70	-52	12	76	-58	12	82	216
25	26	-15	27	28	-19	29	30	-23	31	32	-27	33	34	-31	35	36	-35	216
63	-14	-13	67	-16	-15	71	-18	-17	75	-20	-19	79	-22	-21	83	-24	-23	216
-64	12	88	-70	12	94	-76	12	100	-82	12	106	-88	12	112	-94	12	118	216
37	38	-39	39	40	-43	41	42	-47	43	44	-51	45	46	-55	47	48	-59	216
87	-26	-25	91	-28	-27	95	-30	-29	99	-32	-31	103	-34	-33	107	-36	-35	216
-100	12	124	-106	12	130	-112	12	136	-118	12	142	-124	12	148	-130	12	154	216
49	50	-63	51	52	-67	53	54	-71	55	56	-75	57	58	-79	59	60	-83	216
111	-38	-37	115	-40	-39	119	-42	-41	123	-44	-43	127	-46	-45	131	-48	-47	216
-136	12	160	-142	12	166	-148	12	172	-154	12	178	-160	12	184	-166	12	190	216
61	62	-87	63	64	-91	65	66	-95	67	68	-99	69	70	-103	71	72	-107	216
216	216	216	216	216	216	216	216	216	216	216	216	216	216	216	216	216	216	216

It is a self-made magic square of order 18 formed by equal sums magic squares of order 3.

For more studied toward this direction see the author's work [59, 60, 61, 62, 63, 64, 65, 66].

3.7 Double-Digit Algebraic Striped Magic Squares of Order 18

Below are three different ways of writing magic square of order 18, i.e., **cyclic**, **flat** and **cornered**.

3.7.1 Cyclic-Type

Result 3. *An algebraic striped magic square of order 18 in cyclic way is given by*

a82	a83	a84	a85	a86	a87	a88	a89	a90	a91	a92	a93	a94	a95	a96	$8*m-a96-a95-a94-a93-a92-a91-a90-a89-a88-a87-a86-a85-a84-a83-a82$	m-a97	a97	
m-a82	m-a83	m-a84	m-a85	m-a86	m-a87	m-a88	m-a89	m-a90	m-a91	m-a92	m-a93	m-a94	m-a95	m-a96	$a96+a95+a94+a93+a92+a91+a90+a89+a88+a87+a86+a85+a84+a83+a82-7*m$	m-a98	a98	
$8*m-2*a126+a97-a128-a127-a133-a132-a131-a130-a129-a137-a136-a135-a134-a139-a138-a98$	$2*a126-a97+a128+a127+a133+a132+a131+a130+a129+a137+a136+a135+a134+a139+a138+a98-7*m$															m-a99	a99	
a139	m-a139																m-a100	a100
a138	m-a138																m-a101	a101
a137	m-a137																m-a102	a102
a136	m-a136																m-a103	a103
a135	m-a135																m-a104	a104
a134	m-a134																m-a105	a105
a133	m-a133																m-a106	a106
a132	m-a132																m-a107	a107
a131	m-a131																m-a108	a108
a130	m-a130																m-a109	a109
a129	m-a129																m-a110	a110
a128	m-a128																m-a111	a111
a127	m-a127															$a99+a97+a109+a110+a111+a105+a106+a107+a108+a100+a101+a102+a103+a104+a98-7*m$	$8*m-a99-a97-a109-a110-a111-a105-a106-a107-a108-a100-a101-a102-a103-a104-a98$	
a126	m-a126	$a114+a113+a116+a115+a118+a117+a120+a119+a122+a121+a124+a123+a125+2*a112+a83-a82-7*m$	m-a125	m-a124	m-a123	m-a122	m-a121	m-a120	m-a119	m-a118	m-a117	m-a116	m-a115	m-a114		m-a113	m-a112	m+a82-a83-a112
$a98+a126-a97$	m+a97-a98-a126	$8*m-a114-a113-a116-a115-a118-a117-a120-a119-a122-a121-a124-a123-a125-2*a112-a83+a82$	a125	a124	a123	a122	a121	a120	a119	a118	a117	a116	a115	a114		a113	a112	a83+a112-a82

The internal part of order 14 can be seen in [68]

● Details

It is an **algebraic cyclic striped** magic square of order 18 composed of four equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×16 embedded with a magic square of order 14. The internal part, i.e., magic square of order 14 is as given in Result ???. In this case, the magic sums are $S_{6 \times 6} := 3m$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 5m$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 7m$ and $S_{18 \times 18} := 9m$, where m is the width of the **strip**. See below two examples:

Example 3.25. Below are two examples of **algebraic striped** magic square of order 18 based on Result ??? are given by

18	mgc	Inder J. Taneja	https://inderjtaneja.com/	https://numbers-magic.com/	@IJTANEJA	©IJT	1179												
	82	83	84	85	86	87	88	89	90	91	92	93	94	95	96	-287	34	97	1179
	49	48	47	46	45	44	43	42	41	40	39	38	37	36	35	418	33	98	1179
	-934	1065	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	291	80	51	32	99	1179
	139	-8	91	90	89	88	87	86	85	84	83	82	81	-160	79	52	31	100	1179
	138	-7	-52	183	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	405	110	21	78	53	30	101	1179
	137	-6	81	50	117	116	115	114	113	112	111	-274	109	22	77	54	29	102	1179
	136	-5	80	51	270	-139	378	1	2	3	4	5	108	23	76	55	28	103	1179
	135	-4	79	52	39	92	-247	130	129	128	127	126	107	24	75	56	27	104	1179
	134	-3	78	53	38	93	6	7	8	384	-21	9	106	25	74	57	26	105	1179
	133	-2	77	54	37	94	125	124	123	-253	152	122	105	26	73	58	25	106	1179
	132	-1	76	55	36	95	387	10	-40	11	12	13	104	27	72	59	24	107	1179
	131	0	75	56	35	96	-256	121	171	120	119	118	-225	356	71	60	23	108	1179
	130	1	74	57	34	97	-181	98	99	100	101	102	103	102	70	61	22	109	1179
	129	2	73	58	35	96	312	33	32	31	30	29	28	29	-39	170	21	110	1179
	128	3	72	59	73	60	61	62	63	64	65	66	67	68	69	68	20	111	1179
	127	4	73	58	58	71	70	69	68	67	66	65	64	63	62	63	643	-512	1179
	126	5	855	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	18	1179
	127	4	-724	125	124	123	122	121	120	119	118	117	116	115	114	113	112	113	1179
	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179

18	mgc	Inder J. Taneja	https://inderjtaneja.com/	https://numbers-magic.com/	@IJTANEJA	©IJT	1332												
	82	83	84	85	86	87	88	89	90	91	92	93	94	95	96	-151	51	97	1332
	66	65	64	63	62	61	60	59	58	57	56	55	54	53	52	299	50	98	1332
	-798	946	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	393	97	51	49	99	1332
	139	9	108	107	106	105	104	103	102	101	100	99	98	-245	96	52	48	100	1332
	138	10	50	98	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	473	127	21	95	53	47	101	1332
	137	11	81	67	134	133	132	131	130	129	128	-325	126	22	94	54	46	102	1332
	136	12	80	68	338	-190	429	1	2	3	4	5	125	23	93	55	45	103	1332
	135	13	79	69	39	109	-281	147	146	145	144	143	124	24	92	56	44	104	1332
	134	14	78	70	38	110	6	7	8	435	-21	9	123	25	91	57	43	105	1332
	133	15	77	71	37	111	142	141	140	-287	169	139	122	26	90	58	42	106	1332
	132	16	76	72	36	112	438	10	-40	11	12	13	121	27	89	59	41	107	1332
	131	17	75	73	35	113	-290	138	188	137	136	135	-276	424	88	60	40	108	1332
	130	18	74	74	34	114	-232	115	116	117	118	119	120	119	87	61	39	109	1332
	129	19	73	75	35	113	380	33	32	31	30	29	28	29	-124	272	38	110	1332
	128	20	72	76	-12	77	78	79	80	81	82	83	84	85	86	85	37	111	1332
	127	21	73	75	160	71	70	69	68	67	66	65	64	63	62	63	524	-376	1332
	126	22	736	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	35	1332
	127	21	-588	125	124	123	122	121	120	119	118	117	116	115	114	113	112	113	1332
	1332	1332	1332	1332	1332	1332	1332	1332	1332	1332	1332	1332	1332	1332	1332	1332	1332	1332	1332

Above there are two examples. In both the cases, the magic sums are:

(i) *First Example:* $S_{6 \times 6} := 393, S_{10 \times 10} := 655, S_{14 \times 14} := 917, S_{18 \times 18} := 1179$ and $m := 131$.

(ii) *Second Example:* $S_{6 \times 6} := 444, S_{10 \times 10} := 740, S_{14 \times 14} := 1036, S_{18 \times 18} := 1332$ and $m := 148$.

3.7.2 Flat-Type

Result 4. *An algebraic striped magic square of order 18 in flat way is given by*

a81	a82	a83	a84	a85	a86	a87	a88	a89	a90	a91	a92	a93	a94	a95	$9m - a97 - a96 - a95 - a94 - a93 - a92 - a91 - a90 - a89 - a88 - a87 - a86 - a85 - a84 - a83 - a82 - a81$	a96	a97	
m-a81	m-a82	m-a83	m-a84	m-a85	m-a86	m-a87	m-a88	m-a89	m-a90	m-a91	m-a92	m-a93	m-a94	m-a95	$a97 + a96 + a95 + a94 + a93 + a92 + a91 + a90 + a89 + a88 + a87 + a86 + a85 + a84 + a83 + a82 + a81 - 8m$	m-a96	m-a97	
$7m - a129 - a128 - a136 - a135 - a134 - a133 - a132 - a138 - a137 - a127 - a126 - a131 - a130$	$a129 + a128 + a136 + a135 + a134 + a133 + a132 + a138 + a137 + a127 + a126 + a131 + a130 - 6m$															m-a98	a98	
a138	m-a138																m-a99	a99
a137	m-a137																m-a100	a100
a136	m-a136																m-a101	a101
a135	m-a135																m-a102	a102
a134	m-a134																m-a103	a103
a133	m-a133																m-a104	a104
a132	m-a132																m-a105	a105
a131	m-a131																m-a106	a106
a130	m-a130																m-a107	a107
a129	m-a129																m-a108	a108
a128	m-a128																m-a109	a109
a127	m-a127																m-a110	a110
a126	m-a126																$a98 + a99 + a110 + a106 + a107 + a108 + a109 + a102 + a103 + a104 + a105 + a100 + a101 - 6m$	$7m - a98 - a99 - a110 - a106 - a107 - a108 - a109 - a102 - a103 - a104 - a105 - a100 - a101$
$m + a97 - a96 - a125$	m-a125	$a82 + a112 + 2a111 + a114 + a113 + a116 + a115 + a118 + a117 + a120 + a119 + a122 + a121 + a124 + a123 + 2a125 + a96 - a97 - 8m - a81$	m-a124	m-a123	m-a122	m-a121	m-a120	m-a119	m-a118	m-a117	m-a116	m-a115	m-a114	m-a113		m-a112	m-a111	$m + a81 - a82 - a111$
$a96 + a125 - a97$	a125	$9m + a81 - a82 - a112 - 2a111 - a114 - a113 - a116 - a115 - a118 - a117 - a120 - a119 - a122 - a121 - a124 - a123 - 2a125 - a96 + a97$	a124	a123	a122	a121	a120	a119	a118	a117	a116	a115	a114	a113		a112	a111	$a82 + a111 - a81$

The internal part of order 14 can be seen in [68]

● Details

It is an algebraic flat striped magic square of order 18 composed of two equal sums magic rectangles of orders 2×18 and two magic rectangles of order 2×14 embedded with a magic square of order 14. This magic square of order 14 is exactly the same as given in the Result ???. In this case the magic sums are $S_{6 \times 6} := 3m$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 5m$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 7m$ and $S_{18 \times 18} := 9m$, where m is the width of the **strip**. See below two examples:

Example 3.26. Below are two examples of algebraic striped magic square of order 18 based on Result 4 are given by

18	mgc	Inder J. Taneja		https://inderjtaneja.com/				https://numbers-magic.com/				@IJTANEJA	©IJT	1251					
	81	82	83	84	85	86	87	88	89	90	91	92	93	94	95	-262	96	97	1251
	58	57	56	55	54	53	52	51	50	49	48	47	46	45	44	401	43	42	1251
	-743	882	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	388	50	51	41	98	1251
	138	1	100	99	98	97	96	95	94	93	92	91	90	-249	89	88	40	99	1251
	137	2	11	128	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	542	20	21	87	52	39	100	1251
	136	3	80	59	126	125	124	123	122	121	120	-403	119	118	86	53	38	101	1251
	135	4	79	60	237	-98	1	138	4	135	7	132	117	22	85	54	37	102	1251
	134	5	78	61	38	101	2	137	263	-124	8	131	116	23	84	55	36	103	1251
	133	6	77	62	37	102	3	136	5	134	254	-115	115	24	83	56	35	104	1251
	132	7	76	63	36	103	272	-133	6	133	9	130	114	25	82	57	34	105	1251
	131	8	75	64	35	104	131	129	128	-223	127	125	113	26	81	58	33	106	1251
	130	9	74	65	34	105	8	10	11	362	12	14	-158	297	80	59	32	107	1251
	129	10	73	66	107	106	-286	107	108	109	110	111	112	111	79	60	31	108	1251
	128	11	72	67	32	33	425	32	31	30	29	28	27	28	-52	191	30	109	1251
	127	12	69	68	24	69	70	71	72	73	74	75	76	77	78	77	29	110	1251
	126	13	70	71	115	70	69	68	67	66	65	64	63	62	61	62	518	-379	1251
	15	14	894	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	27	1251
	124	125	-755	124	123	122	121	120	119	118	117	116	115	114	113	112	111	112	1251
	1251	1251	1251	1251	1251	1251	1251	1251	1251	1251	1251	1251	1251	1251	1251	1251	1251	1251	1251

18	mgc	Inder J. Taneja		https://inderjtaneja.com/				https://numbers-magic.com/				@IJTANEJA		©IJT		1368			
	81	82	83	84	85	86	87	88	89	90	91	92	93	94	95	-145	96	97	1368
	71	70	69	68	67	66	65	64	63	62	61	60	59	58	57	297	56	55	1368
	-652	804	39	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	479	50	51	54	98	1368
	138	14	113	112	111	110	109	108	107	106	105	104	103	-327	102	101	53	99	1368
	137	15	76	76	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	607	20	21	100	52	52	100	1368
	136	16	80	72	139	138	137	136	135	134	133	-455	132	131	99	53	51	101	1368
	135	17	79	73	276	-124	1	151	4	148	7	145	130	22	98	54	50	102	1368
	134	18	78	74	38	114	2	150	289	-137	8	144	129	23	97	55	49	103	1368
	133	19	77	75	37	115	3	149	5	147	280	-128	128	24	96	56	48	104	1368
	132	20	76	76	36	116	298	-146	6	146	9	143	127	25	95	57	47	105	1368
	131	21	75	77	35	117	144	142	141	-249	140	138	126	26	94	58	46	106	1368
	130	22	74	78	34	118	8	10	11	401	12	14	-184	336	93	59	45	107	1368
	129	23	73	79	120	119	-338	120	121	122	123	124	125	124	92	60	44	108	1368
	128	24	72	80	32	33	490	32	31	30	29	28	27	28	-104	256	43	109	1368
	127	25	82	81	-54	82	83	84	85	86	87	88	89	90	91	90	42	110	1368
	126	26	70	71	206	70	69	68	67	66	65	64	63	62	61	62	440	-288	1368
	28	27	790	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	37	38	39	40	41	40	1368
	124	125	-638	124	123	122	121	120	119	118	117	116	115	114	113	112	111	112	1368
	1368	1368	1368	1368	1368	1368	1368	1368	1368	1368	1368	1368	1368	1368	1368	1368	1368	1368	1368

Above there are two examples. In both the cases, the magic sums are:

(i) *First Example:* $S_{6 \times 6} := 417, S_{10 \times 10} := 695, S_{14 \times 14} := 973, S_{18 \times 18} := 1251$ and $m := 139$.

(ii) *Second Example:* $S_{6 \times 6} := 456, S_{10 \times 10} := 760, S_{14 \times 14} := 1064, S_{18 \times 18} := 1368$ and $m := 152$.

3.7.3 Cornered

Result 5. *An algebraic striped cornered magic square of order 18 is given by*

																	m-a101	a101	
																		m-a102	a102
																		m-a103	a103
																		m-a104	a104
																		m-a105	a105
																		m-a106	a106
																		m-a107	a107
																		m-a108	a108
																		m-a109	a109
																		m-a110	a110
																		m-a111	a111
																		m-a112	a112
																		m-a113	a113
																		m-a114	a114
																		m-a115	a115
																		a101+a102+a109+a110+a104+a105+a106+a107+a108+a103+a112+a111+a114+a113+a115-7*m	8*m-a101-a102-a109-a110-a104-a105-a106-a107-a108-a103-a112-a111-a114-a113-a115
m+a77-a78+a57-a58+a41-a42-a50+a49-a68+a67-a90+a89+a101-a102-a116	m-a116	m-a117	m-a118	m-a119	m-a120	m-a121	m-a122	m-a123	m-a124	m-a125	m-a126	m-a127	m-a128	m-a129			a78-a57+a58-a41+a42+a50-a49+a68-a67+a90-a89-a101+a102+2*a116+a118+a117+a120+a119+a122+a121+a124+a123+a125-8*m+a129+a128+a127+a126+2*a130-a77	m-a130	m-a130
a78-a57+a58-a41+a42+a50-a49+a68-a67+a90-a89-a101+a102+a116-a77	a116	a117	a118	a119	a120	a121	a122	a123	a124	a125	a126	a127	a128	a129			a77-a78+a57-a58+a41-a42-a50+a49-a68+a67-a90+a89+a101-a102-2*a116-a118-a117-a120-a119-a122-a121-a124-a123-a125+9*m-a129-a128-a127-a126-2*a130	a130	a130

The internal part of order 14 can be seen in [68]

● Details

It is an **algebraic cornered striped** magic square of order 18, where the magic squares of order 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14 and 16 are at the upper-left corner. In this case the magic sums are $S_{4 \times 4} := 2m$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 3m$, $S_{8 \times 8} := 4m$, $S_{10 \times 10} := 5m$, $S_{12 \times 12} := 6m$, $S_{14 \times 14} := 7m$, $S_{16 \times 16} := 8m$ and $S_{18 \times 18} := 9m$, where m is the width of the **strip**. See below two examples:

Example 3.27. Below are two examples of **algebraic striped** magic square of order 18 based on Result 5 are given by

18	mgc	Inder J. Taneja				https://inderjtaneja.com/				https://numbers-magic.com/				@IJTANEJA		©IJT		1179	
	258	1	2	1	5	126	120	11	110	21	96	35	78	53	56	75	30	101	1179
	-127	130	129	130	6	125	119	12	109	22	95	36	77	54	55	76	29	102	1179
	3	4	-1	256	7	124	118	13	108	23	94	37	76	55	54	77	28	103	1179
	128	127	132	-125	244	-113	117	14	107	24	93	38	75	56	53	78	27	104	1179
	381	123	122	-475	121	121	116	15	106	25	92	39	74	57	52	79	26	105	1179
	-250	8	9	606	10	10	-197	328	105	26	91	40	73	58	51	80	25	106	1179
	-246	115	114	113	112	94	111	111	104	27	90	41	72	59	50	81	24	107	1179
	377	16	17	18	19	37	20	20	-225	356	89	42	71	60	49	82	23	108	1179
	100	103	102	101	100	99	98	-242	97	97	88	43	70	61	48	83	22	109	1179
	31	28	29	30	31	32	33	373	34	34	-173	304	69	62	47	84	21	110	1179
	-247	87	86	85	84	83	82	81	80	207	79	79	68	63	46	85	20	111	1179
	378	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	-76	52	52	-17	148	45	86	19	112	1179
	62	67	66	65	64	63	62	61	60	59	58	116	57	57	44	87	18	113	1179
	69	64	65	66	67	68	69	70	71	72	73	15	74	74	267	-136	17	114	1179
	-631	43	42	41	40	39	38	37	36	35	34	33	32	1167	31	31	16	115	1179
	762	88	89	90	91	92	93	94	95	96	97	98	99	-1036	100	100	703	-572	1179
	8	15	14	13	12	11	10	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1050	1	1	1179
	123	116	117	118	119	120	121	122	123	124	125	126	127	128	129	-919	130	130	1179
	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179	1179

18	mgc	Inder J. Taneja				https://inderjtaneja.com/				https://numbers-magic.com/				@IJTANEJA		©IJT		1296	
	284	1	2	1	5	139	133	11	123	21	109	35	91	53	69	75	43	101	1296
	-140	143	142	143	6	138	132	12	122	22	108	36	90	54	68	76	42	102	1296
	3	4	-1	282	7	137	131	13	121	23	107	37	89	55	67	77	41	103	1296
	141	140	145	-138	270	-126	130	14	120	24	106	38	88	56	66	78	40	104	1296
	420	136	135	-527	134	134	129	15	119	25	105	39	87	57	65	79	39	105	1296
	-276	8	9	671	10	10	-223	367	118	26	104	40	86	58	64	80	38	106	1296
	-272	128	127	126	125	94	124	124	117	27	103	41	85	59	63	81	37	107	1296
	416	16	17	18	19	50	20	20	-264	408	102	42	84	60	62	82	36	108	1296
	113	116	115	114	113	112	111	-294	110	110	101	43	83	61	61	83	35	109	1296
	31	28	29	30	31	32	33	438	34	34	-225	369	82	62	60	84	34	110	1296
	-286	100	99	98	97	96	95	94	93	194	92	92	81	63	59	85	33	111	1296
	430	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	-50	52	52	-82	226	58	86	32	112	1296
	75	80	79	78	77	76	75	74	73	72	71	38	70	70	57	87	31	113	1296
	69	64	65	66	67	68	69	70	71	72	73	106	74	74	189	-45	30	114	1296
	-735	56	55	54	53	52	51	50	49	48	47	46	45	1193	44	44	29	115	1296
	879	88	89	90	91	92	93	94	95	96	97	98	99	-1049	100	100	612	-468	1296
	21	28	27	26	25	24	23	22	21	20	19	18	17	16	15	946	14	14	1296
	123	116	117	118	119	120	121	122	123	124	125	126	127	128	129	-802	130	130	1296
	1296	1296	1296	1296	1296	1296	1296	1296	1296	1296	1296	1296	1296	1296	1296	1296	1296	1296	1296

Above there are two examples. In both the cases, the magic sums are:

- (i) **First Example:** $S_{4 \times 4} := 262, S_{6 \times 6} := 393, S_{8 \times 8} := 524, S_{10 \times 10} := 655, S_{12 \times 12} := 786, S_{14 \times 14} := 917, S_{16 \times 16} := 1048, S_{18 \times 18} := 1179$ and $m := 131$.
- (ii) **Second Example:** $S_{4 \times 4} := 288, S_{6 \times 6} := 432, S_{8 \times 8} := 576, S_{10 \times 10} := 720, S_{12 \times 12} := 864, S_{14 \times 14} := 1008, S_{16 \times 16} := 1152, S_{18 \times 18} := 1296$ and $m := 144$.

For more details refer Taneja [67, 68].

4 Author's Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation of Numbers

For author's contribution to **magic squares** and **recreation of numbers** please see the links below:

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